

22RPT04 RFMicrowave2

D4: Final reports on the interlaboratory comparisons on (i) Equivalent capacitance substitution method (ECSM) for monopole antennas, (ii) antennas in the frequency range 30 MHz – 1 GHz, (iii) High-frequency calibration using a fully anechoic room (FAR)/ free space (FS) in the range 1 GHz – 40 GHz.

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Glossary

AF	Antenna factor
AUT	Antenna Under Test
CISPR	Comité International Spécial des Perturbations Radioélectriques
CRV	Comparison Reference Value
DoE	Degrees of Equivalence
EMI	Electromagnetic Interference
HF	High frequency
ECSM	Equivalent Capacitor Substitution Method
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
EU	European Union
LPDA	Log Periodic Dipole Antennas
MAD	Median of Absolute Deviations
NMI	National Metrology Institute
OATS	Open Area Test Site
RF	Radio Frequency
SIL	Site Insertion Loss
SLA	Small Loop Antenna
SSM	Standard Site Method
TEM	Transversal Electromagnetic (e.g., wave)
VNA	Vector Network Analyser

Summary

Within the project 22RPT04 RF Microwave 2, a EURAMET project started on May 01, 2023, a supplementary comparison was conducted for the calibration of Antenna Factors (AF) for several different types of antennas. The involved partners in this comparison are TÜBİTAK UME (Türkiye), CMI (Czech Republic), SIQ (Slovenia) and RISE (Sweden). The outcome of this comparison is to be deliverable D4 in the project.

The different antennas cover the frequency range 9 kHz - 40 GHz and are calibrated using different methods. The calibrations have been divided into three different sub-groups. These are:

- Calibrations using the Equivalent Capacitor Substitution Method (ECSM). This method is used for calibrating monopole antennas in the frequency range 9 kHz to 30 MHz.
- Calibrations using an Open Area Test Site (OATS). This method is primarily used in the frequency range 30 MHz to 1 GHz on broadband antennas such as, for instance, Biconical Antennas and Log Periodic Dipole Antennas (LPDA).
- Calibrations using Free Space conditions. This is used for antennas in the range 1 GHz to 40 GHz, mainly for horn antennas, hybrid antennas whose part is over 1 GHz and some precision biconical antennas. Only horn antennas were used in this comparison.

This comparison report has been divided into these three categories, with one different NMI responsible as the pilot for each category. Each category has its own report, which are chapters 1-3 in this document.

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For further details about the RFMicrowave 2 project see the project website <https://rfmwii.cmi.gov.cz/>

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1. COMPARISON OF ANTENNA FACTOR (AF) FOR MONOPOLE ANTENNA USING EQUIVALENT CAPACITANCE SUBSTITUTION METHOD (ECSM)

Partners: TÜBİTAK UME, RISE, SIQ

May 2025

1.1 Introduction

The subject of this intercomparison is the calibration of antenna factor (AF) for monopole antennas in the frequency range between 9 kHz and 30 MHz using the Equivalent Capacitance Substitution Method (ECSM) according to ANSI IEEE C63.5 (2017), CISPR 16-1-6 (2014) and/or SAE ARP 958, Rev. E. Each laboratory can decide whether to use a VNA method or method using a signal generator and measuring receiver.

The standards ANSI IEEE C63.5 (2017), CISPR 16-1-6 (2014) and SAE ARP 958 rev E clearly define the capacitance which should be used in the ECSM adaptor. On the contrary, SAE ARP 958, Rev. D standard only specifies 10 pF capacitor for a 1 m long rod. Each participant laboratory can decide according to which standard the intercomparison was performed. Moreover, the calibration can be repeated for different standards.

1.1.1 Traveling standards

The traveling standard which will be used for intercomparison is monopole antenna ETS Lindgren model 3301C, s.n.: 00152392 which will be provided by TÜBİTAK UME, Fig. 1-1. The working range of the antenna is between 9 kHz and 30 MHz. The rod length is 104 cm and the rod diameter is 5 mm and these values should be used for the calculation of ideal capacitance in ECSM adaptor.

Fig. 1-1 Monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C (a), calibration fixture with nominal capacitance 12 pF (b) and monopole antenna with calibration fixture (c)

1.1.2 Participating institutes

Three different laboratories will be included in the intercomparison, Tab. 1-1. The monopole antenna will be provided by TÜBİTAK UME. The pilot institute for this comparison is TÜBİTAK UME (Türkiye).

Tab. 1-1 Participant laboratories

Acronym	Shipping Address	Contact Person
TÜBİTAK UME (pilot)	Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü (UME) TÜBİTAK Gebze Yerleşkesi Barış Mah. Dr. Zeki Acar Cad. No:1 41470 Gebze-Kocaeli, Türkiye	Mehmet Çınar mehmet.cinar@tubitak.gov.tr Tel: +90 262 679 50 00
RISE	Research Institutes of Sweden Brinellgatan 4 504 62 Borås Sweden	Mats Cedheim mats.cedheim@ri.se Tel: +46 10 516 60 86
SIQ	Slovenian institute of quality and metrology Mašera-Spasičeva ulica 10 1000 Ljubljana Slovenia	Marko Berginc marko.berginc@siq.si Tel: +386 1 4778 340

1.1.3 Time schedule

The time schedule for the comparison is given in the Tab. 1-2. The circulation of the travelling standard will be organized in a single loop style. Each laboratory will have two weeks to carry out the measurements. Any deviation in the agreed plan should be approved by the pilot institute.

After completing the measurements (maximum two weeks), each laboratory will arrange the delivery of the equipment to the next participant in the schedule list. The shipping within EU and NON-EU countries is expected to be one and two weeks, respectively. The planned schedule is also gathered in Tab. 1-2. The travelling standard should be checked for damage immediately after reception. In case of damage, the pilot laboratory should be informed immediately.

The brief schedule for the intercomparison is as follows:

- TUBITAK will perform initial measurements and will send the antenna to RISE,
- RISE will perform the measurements and send the antenna to SIQ,
- SIQ will perform the measurements and return antenna to RISE,
- RISE will ship antenna back to TUBITAK together with other antennas which are part of other intercomparisons,
- after receiving the antenna, TUBITAK will repeat the measurements.

Tab. 1-2 Circulation time schedule

Acronym	Activity	Start date	End date
TÜBİTAK UME	Measurement at TÜBİTAK UME	23.4.2024	17.5.2024
	Shipping from TÜBİTAK to RISE	17.5.2024	3.6.2024
RISE	Measurement at RISE	3.6.2024	14.6.2024
	Shipping from RISE to SIQ	14.6.2024	24.6.2024
SIQ	Measurement at SIQ	24.6.2024	5.7.2024
	Shipping from SIQ to RISE	5.7.2024	15.7.2024
	Shipping from RISE to TÜBİTAK UME	15.7.2024	29.7.2024
TÜBİTAK UME	Measurement at TÜBİTAK UME	29.7.2024	9.8.2024

1.1.4 Transport case

The travelling standards and miscellaneous equipment that will be sent from TÜBİTAK to RISE will travel in a well-protected package whose dimensions are approximately (107 cm length × 92 cm width × 93 cm height) and a weight, including the travelling standards, of approx. 108 kg. The transport case can easily be opened for customs inspection. The content of the transport case is:

- biconical antenna,
- log periodic antenna,
- monopole antenna,
- horn antenna,
- technical protocol of the comparison of open area test site antenna measurements,
- ATA carnet.

After receiving the carrying case, RISE will check for any damage the items inside of the box. If the travelling standards have any damage due to transportation, this situation will be reported to all participant included in the intercomparison. After completing the measurements, RISE will send the monopole antenna to SIQ using a smaller box and will use the original box to send other antennas to CMI (not part of this intercomparison). SIQ will return the antenna to RISE using the same small box. After completing all intercomparison, RISE will collect all antennas and send them to back to TÜBİTAK using the original package.

1.1.5 Transportation of travelling standard

The participants will be responsible for arranging the transportation to the next participant. Each participant laboratory is responsible for the transportation costs to the following participant laboratory in the list, for its own cost for the measurements, as well as any damage that may occur within its country. The overall costs for the organisation of the comparison are covered by the pilot laboratory. The pilot laboratory has no insurance for any loss or damage of the travelling standard, except for the insurance related to the delivery to the first participant in the list (first transportation of the standards). The estimated cost of the travelling standard and miscellaneous equipment is 42.800 € (the value needed for the carrier company to include a transportation insurance covering any damage caused to the equipment).

After arrival in the participant's laboratory, the standard and accompanying instrumentation should be checked and allowed to stabilise in a temperature and humidity-controlled room for at least one day before use. The participants shall inform the pilot laboratory by e-mail when the travelling standards have arrived by filling the form (Tab. 1-3). The participants shall also inform the next recipient and the pilot institute by e-mail about the shipment of the travelling standards by filling the form (Tab. 1-4). In case of any damage or malfunction of the travelling standards inform the TÜBİTAK, RISE and SIQ about the damage. In that case, the comparison will be carried out after the travelling standard is repaired or supply with a new standard.

Tab. 1-3 Sample form for the information of arrival of the travelling standards

Confirmation Note for Receipt		
Date of Arrival		
NMI		
Name of Responsible Person		
Traveling standard	<input type="checkbox"/> Damaged	<input type="checkbox"/> Not Damaged
Additional Notes:		

Tab. 1-4 Sample form for the information of dispatch of the travelling standard

Confirmation Note for Dispatch	
Date of Shipment	
NMI	
Name of Responsible Person	
Shipment Information (company name etc.)	
Additional Notes:	

1.2 Measurement points and conditions

1.2.1 Measuring points and frequency list

The calibration of antenna factor (AF) for monopole antennas should be performed between 9 kHz and 30 MHz. The number of measuring points should be large enough to obtain a smooth curve. For the intercomparison a frequency list proposed by the standard should be used, Tab. 1-5.

Tab. 1-5 Frequency points where the calibration of monopole antennas should be performed.

Frequency range	Increments
9 kHz to 10 kHz	1 kHz
10 kHz to 150 kHz	10 kHz
150 kHz to 200 kHz	50 kHz
200 kHz to 1 MHz	100 kHz
1 MHz to 30 (50) MHz	1 MHz

Tab. 1-6 Measurement points.

Frequency (MHz)	AF(dB) (1/m)	Unc. (dB) ($k=2$)	Ambient Temperature (°C)	Ambient Humidity (%rh)
0.009				
0.01				
0.02				
0.03				
...				
...				
...				
30				

1.2.2 Before the Measurements

- Monopole antenna should be allowed to stabilize in a temperature and humidity-controlled environment for at least 1 day before commencing measurements.
- Before the measurements, mechanical controls of the antennas should be done.
- Avoid extreme temperature, humidity or pressure changes as well as violent impacts
- All type of the measurement instruments, which have 230 V AC power suppliers must plug in to power supplier at least 120 minutes before calibration.

1.2.3 Environmental conditions

- The ambient temperature and humidity must be measured. No corrections will be performed for temperature and humidity effects.
- Preferably, the measurements should be carried out at the ambient conditions given below:
 - temperature: $23\text{ °C} \pm 2\text{ °C}$
 - relative humidity: $50\% \pm 20\%$

1.3 Reporting

Each participant should provide the following information to RISE no later than 20 days after completing the measurements. The report must include at least:

- participant information,
- measurement date,
- detailed description of the measurement method and system used, including the details for the ECSM capacitor calculation,
- measurement standards used in the comparison measurements,
- measurement results,
- environmental conditions during the measurements (temperature, relative humidity),

- calculation example and uncertainty budget estimated for a confidence level of 95%,
- traceability.

The measurement uncertainty of measurement shall be calculated according to the JCGM 100 Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement for the coverage probability of 95% (in the case of infinite degrees of freedom or an assumed Gaussian probability density function, which corresponds to a coverage factor $k=2$). The uncertainty of measurement defined by the Monte Carlo Simulation must be also calculated for the confidence level of 95%. The measurement report or calibration certificate of each participant should include and briefly describe all contributions to the measurement uncertainty or at least the most relevant ones according to the format given in Annex A1.

1.4 Analysis of all results and final report

After completing the measurements, the final report should be sent to RISE who will collect all reports for further processing for the comparison results. RISE and SIQ are responsible for the preparation of a comparison report. The draft A version of the comparison report will be issued within two months after reception of participants results. Afterwards, Draft A Report will be sent to the participants for discussion, amendment if applicable, and eventually for approval.

The participants will have two weeks to send their comments about Draft Report A. After all potential amendments have been considered, and after final approval by all participants, Draft A Report will become the Final Report.

Comparison results will be evaluated according to the Degree-Of-Equivalence (DoE) E_n value which is calculated using (1.1), where V_{LAB} denotes participant laboratory measurement result, V_{CRV} reference value of the comparison, U_{LAB} participant laboratory measurement uncertainty, and U_{CRV} uncertainty associated to the CRV.

$$E_n = \frac{|V_{LAB} - V_{CRV}|}{\sqrt{U_{LAB}^2 + U_{CRV}^2}} \quad (1.1)$$

The *Comparison Reference Value* (CRV) for each frequency will be calculated using robust analysis of results by using *Algorithm A in Annex C* where no discarding of outlier participants is made, and all results of the participant laboratories are included in the analysis. In this case, the mean of all three participant laboratories (TÜBİTAK, RISE and SIQ) will be used to calculate the CRV.

The outlier's methodology will not be defined since only three laboratories are included in the intercomparison. In this method the determination of outliers is based on the 3·MAD criterion, which makes use of the median of all participants and of the calculated Median of Absolute Deviations (MAD). Those participants whose difference with respect to the Median is demonstrated to be more than three times the Median of Absolute Deviations is considered as outliers, and as such is not considered in the determination of the Weighted Mean and thus of the CRV.

The laboratory measurement results will be utilized according to the evaluation criteria for the E_n which are given below:

If $|E_n| \leq 1$ then it is successful

If $|E_n| > 1$ then it is unsuccessful

1.5 References

- [1.1] CCEM Guidelines for Planning, Organizing, Conducting and Reporting Key, Supplementary and Pilot Comparisons, 2007 (available on the BIPM website:
http://www.bipm.org/utis/common/pdf/CC/CCEM/ccem_guidelines.pdf
- [1.2] Evaluation of measurement data – Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM), JCGM 100:2008, First edition, September 2008 (available on BIPM website:
http://www.bipm.org/utis/common/documents/jcgm/JCGM_100_2008_E.pdf
- [1.3] UNE-EN ISO/IEC 17043:2010: “Conformity assessment — General requirements for proficiency testing”, *International Standardization Organization*, 2010
- [1.4] International Standard ISO 13528: “*Statistical Methods for Use in Proficiency Testing by Interlaboratory Comparison*”. Reference number ISO 13528:2015
- [1.5] EA-4/02, Expression of the Uncertainty of Measurement in Calibration, September 2013, (rev. 01)
- [1.6] CISPR 16-1-6, Edition 1.1 (2017), Specification for radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus and methods - Part 1-6: Radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus - EMC antenna calibration.
- [1.7] ANSI C63.5 (2017), American National Standard for Electromagnetic Compatibility – Radiated Emission Measurements in Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) Control – Calibration of Antennas (9 kHz to 40 GHz)
- [1.8] SAE ARP958 REV.E, Electromagnetic interference measurement antennas, calibration method

1.6 Reports from the partners

1.6.1 TÜBİTAK UME

The measurements were performed by Mehmet Çınar, Serdar Büyük, Çağlar Aslan from TÜBİTAK UME between 11. October 2024 and 14. October 2024. The contact details are given in Tab. 1-7.

Tab. 1-7 Participant information

Institute Name	TÜBİTAK UME
Contact Person	Mehmet Çınar, Serdar Büyük, Çağlar Aslan
Phone No.	+90 262 679 50 00
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e-mail	mehmet.cinar@tubitak.gov.tr serdar.buyuk@tubitak.gov.tr caclar.aslan@tubitak.gov.tr
Address	TÜBİTAK Gebze Yerleşkesi, Barış Mah. Dr. Zeki Acar Cad. No:1 41470 Gebze-Kocaeli Türkiye

1.6.1.1 Measurement procedure

The rod antenna measurements were performed for 5 mm rod diameter, 104 cm rod height in accordance with the equivalent capacitance substitution method (ECSM) [1.1], [1.2], [1.3]. For this reason, the nominal capacitance 12 pF calibration kit specified in the protocol was used during the calibration process. Also, the measurements were carried out using 50 Ω low-loss RF cables, 10 dB attenuators and 50 Ω termination during the calibration process. After the measurement setup was prepared, measurements were performed using the network analyser (Fig. 1-2, Fig. 1-3).

In the first step, the output of the rod antenna was terminated with a 50 Ω load and the normalization measurement (V_1) was performed from the signal generator and receiver ports of the capacitor (Fig. 1-2). In the second step, the receiver port of the capacitor was terminated with 50 Ω termination and the measurement was performed from the signal generator of the capacitor and output of the rod antenna (V_2) (Fig. 1-3). Finally, the antenna factor AF was calculated using eq. (1.2) [1.1], [1.2], [1.3].

$$AF = V_1 - V_2 - L_h + CFIL, \quad (1.2)$$

where

- AF is the antenna factor in dB(1/m),
- L_h is the height correction factor in dB(m),
- V_1 is the normalization measurement in dB(μ V),
- V_2 is the rod antenna measurement in dB(μ V),
- $CFIL$ is the 3301CAL fixture insertion loss in dB.

L_h is the effective height factor and was calculated using (1.3), (1.4) versus frequency for a rod length of 104 cm [1.1], [1.2], [1.3].

$$h_e = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi} \cdot \tan \frac{\pi \cdot h}{\lambda}, \quad (1.3)$$

$$L_h = 20 \cdot \log h_e, \quad (1.4)$$

where

- h_e effective height of the rod, in m,
- λ wavelength, in m,
- h actual height of the rod, in m.

For example, at a frequency of 10 kHz, the effective height h_e for a rod with $h = 104$ cm is 0.52 m. The correction factor obtained according to the effective height is $L_h = 5.68$ dB(m). The capacitance value was calculated using the eq. (1.5) vs. frequency for a rod length of 104 cm and a rod diameter of 5 mm [1.6]-[1.8] for uncertainty calculations. For example, at the frequency of 10 kHz, the capacitance value 11.5 pF for 104 cm rod length and 5 mm rod diameter.

$$C_a = 55.6 \cdot \frac{h}{\ln(h/a)-1} \cdot \frac{\tan(2\pi \cdot h/\lambda)}{2\pi \cdot h/\lambda}, \quad (1.5)$$

where

- C_a capacitance of the dummy load, in pF,
- a radius of the rod, in m.

Fig. 1-2 Measurement set-up (left) and example photo (right) for normalization measurement (V_1)

Fig. 1-3 Measurement set-up (left) and example photo (right) for rod antenna measurement (V_2)

1.6.1.2 Equipment

The equipment that was used during the calibration is listed in Tab. 1-8 and the uncertainty calculation example is given in Tab. 1-9.

Tab. 1-8 Standards used in measurements.

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No.
-------------------	--------------	--------------	------------

Network Analyzer	Keysight	E5061B	MY49407095
50 Ohm Termination	Keysight	85032-60018	56412
10 dB Coaxial Fixed Attenuator	Keysight	8491B	MY39271760
10 dB Coaxial Fixed Attenuator	Keysight	8491B	MY39271778
12 pF Calibration Fixture	ETS-LINDGREN	3301CAL	00206934

Tab. 1-9 Measurement uncertainty budget

Uncertainty budget in the frequency range of 9 kHz - 30 MHz						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	<i>k</i> -factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard unc. contribution (dB)
Receiver reading accuracy after direct connection of cables with adapter	B	0.090	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.052
Receiver reading accuracy for antenna measurement	B	0.070	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.040
Generator-receiver (direct connection mismatch with an adapter)	B	0.013	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	1	0.009
Generator-receiver (mismatch for antenna measurement with an adapter)	B	0.129	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	1	0.091
Stability of amplifier gain	B	0.050	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.029
Accuracy of capacitance	B	0.583	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.337
Repeatability	A	0.064	Normal	1	1	0.064
Total Uncertainty (<i>k</i>=2)						0.72

1.6.1.3 Measurements results

Measurements results are shown in Tab. 1-10. The ambient temperature and relative humidity during the calibration were $22\text{ °C} \pm 2\text{ °C}$ and $45\% \pm 10\%$, respectively.

Tab. 1-10 Measurement results

Frequency (MHz)	AF dB (1/m)	Unc. (dB) (k=2)	Frequency (MHz)	AF dB (1/m)	Unc. (dB) (k=2)
0.009	-1.61	0.72	4	-1.91	0.72
0.01	-1.62		5	-1.90	
0.02	-1.66		6	-1.88	
0.03	-1.66		7	-1.85	
0.04	-1.70		8	-1.82	
0.05	-1.72		9	-1.78	
0.06	-1.73		10	-1.74	
0.07	-1.74		11	-1.69	
0.08	-1.74		12	-1.63	
0.09	-1.75		13	-1.58	
0.10	-1.75		14	-1.52	
0.11	-1.76		15	-1.45	
0.12	-1.76		16	-1.39	
0.13	-1.76		17	-1.32	
0.14	-1.77		18	-1.25	
0.15	-1.77		19	-1.17	
0.2	-1.79		20	-1.10	
0.3	-1.81		21	-1.02	
0.4	-1.83		22	-0.94	
0.5	-1.85		23	-0.85	
0.6	-1.86		24	-0.77	
0.7	-1.87		25	-0.69	
0.8	-1.88		26	-0.60	
0.9	-1.89		27	-0.52	
1	-1.89		28	-0.43	
2	-1.92		29	-0.34	
3	-1.92		30	-0.26	

1.6.2 RISE

The measurements were performed by Mats Cedheim from RISE between 6. June 2024 and 7. June 2024. The contact details are given in Tab. 1-11.

Tab. 1-11 Participant information

Institute Name	RISE
Contact	Mats Cedheim
Phone No.	+46 10 516 60 86
e-mail	mats.cedheim@ri.se
Address	Brinellgatan 4 504 62 Boras Sweden

1.6.2.1 Measurement procedure

The method used for the calibration of active monopole antennas is the Equivalent Capacitance Substitution Method (ECSM). The calibration method is based on the substitution of the antenna rod for a calibration fixture. The fixture makes the monopole amplifier see an equivalent impedance as the rod in free space. The difference in power from the amplifier and the fixture gives the antenna factor, after corrections for the fixture and the impedance between the rod and free space. The first step is to determine the capacitor value that is equivalent to the antenna rod. This is done according to (1.6). The effective height of the antenna h_e is then calculated according to (1.7) and the height correction factor is then calculated as defined by (1.8).

$$C_a = 55.6 \cdot \frac{h}{\ln(h/a) - 1} \cdot \frac{\tan(2 \cdot \pi \cdot h / \lambda)}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot h / \lambda}, \quad (1.6)$$

$$h_e = \frac{\lambda}{2 \cdot \pi} \tan \frac{\pi \cdot h}{\lambda}, \quad (1.7)$$

$$L_h = 20 \cdot \log(h_e), \quad (1.8)$$

where

h actual height of the rod antenna, in m,

a actual radius of the rod antenna, in m,

λ wavelength, in m.

Fig. 1-4 Setup using the VNA

Connect according to Fig. 4. First the port 2 of the VNA is connected to (1) in Fig. 1-4, and then the to (2) in Fig. 1-4. The output not used is terminated in 50 Ω. The antenna factor *AF* is then calculated according to (1.9).

$$AF_{dB} = P_{in,dB} - P_{out,dB} + L_h + \Delta U_{dB}, \tag{1.9}$$

where

- AF_{dB} Antenna Factor for the monopole
- $P_{in,dB}$ Output power from the calibration fixture (at 1 in Fig. 4), [2]
- $P_{ut,dB}$ Output power from the monopole (at 2, Fig. 4), [2]
- L_h Height correction factor in dB(m)
- ΔU_{dB} Attenuation of the signal between 1 and input on top of the AUT in Fig. 4

1.6.2.2 Equipment

The equipment that was used during the calibration is listed in Tab. 1-12 and the uncertainty calculation example is given in Tab. 1-13.

Tab. 1-12 Standards used in measurements.

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No.
Network Analyzer	Rohde&Schwarz	ZNB-8	103544
50 Ω termination	Rosenberger	RPC-N	08892
10 dB attenuator	Radiall	R412.710.124	RISE inv.nr: BX81279
10 dB attenuator	Radiall	R412.710.124	RISE inv.nr: BX81280
Calibration Fixture	ETS-Lindgren	3301CAL-B	00269456

Tab. 1-13 Calculation example and uncertainty budget

Uncertainty budget in the frequency range 9 kHz-30 MHz						
source of uncertainty	type (A or B)	value x_i	probability distribution	k -factor	sens. coeff. c_i	standard uncertainty contribution $u(x_i)$
VNA accuracy P_{in}	B	0.0116	Normal	2	1	0.0058
VNA temp drift P_{in}	B	0.0116	Normal	2	1	0.0058
VNA accuracy P_{out}	B	0.0116	Normal	2	1	0.0058
VNA temp drift P_{out}	B	0.0116	Normal	2	1	0.0058
Connector repeatability	A	0.0248	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.0143
Capacitor accuracy	B	0.2078	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.1200
Uncertainty from the rod dimensions	B	0.0404	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	2	0.0467
Mismatch	B	0.0093	U-shaped	$\sqrt{2}$	1	0.0066
Uncertainty in adapter losses	B	0.0114	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	2	0.0067
combined unc.						0.1304
expanded unc. ($k=2$) dB						1.07 dB

1.6.2.3 Measurement results

Measurements results are shown in Tab. 1-14. The ambient temperature and relative humidity during the calibration were $22.1\text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 5\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $44\% \pm 10\%$, respectively.

Tab. 1-14 Measurement results

Frequency (MHz)	AF dB (1/m)	Unc. (dB) ($k=2$)	Frequency (MHz)	AF dB (1/m)	Unc. (dB) ($k=2$)
0.009	-1.560	1.07	4	-1.824	1.07
0.01	-1.576		5	-1.802	
0.02	-1.581		6	-1.782	
0.03	-1.567		7	-1.754	
0.04	-1.604		8	-1.714	
0.05	-1.640		9	-1.673	
0.06	-1.642		10	-1.618	
0.07	-1.644		11	-1.561	
0.08	-1.648		12	-1.510	
0.09	-1.655		13	-1.445	
0.10	-1.660		14	-1.381	
0.11	-1.658		15	-1.310	
0.12	-1.664		16	-1.234	
0.13	-1.671		17	-1.154	
0.14	-1.672		18	-1.072	
0.15	-1.672		19	-0.994	

0.2	-1.693		20	-0.895	
0.3	-1.715		21	-0.808	
0.4	-1.739		22	-0.719	
0.5	-1.758		23	-0.626	
0.6	-1.762		24	-0.531	
0.7	-1.772		25	-0.433	
0.8	-1.783		26	-0.329	
0.9	-1.783		27	-0.226	
1	-1.792		28	-0.121	
2	-1.823		29	-0.012	
3	-1.832		30	0.099	

1.6.3 SIQ

The measurements were performed by Marko Berginc from SIQ on 21. June 2024. The contact details are given in Tab. 1-15.

Tab. 1-15 Participant information

Institute Name	SIQ
Contact Person	Marko Berginc
Phone No.	+386 1 4778 340
e-mail	marko.berginc@siq.si
Address	SIQ Mašera-Spasičeva ulica 10 1000 Ljubljana Slovenia

1.6.3.1 Measurement procedure

The antenna factor AF of monopole antenna is defined by (1.10) in linear form and by (1.11) in logarithmic form, where the V_D denotes the measured output of the signal generator in V or dB(μ V), V_L measured output of the matching unit given in V or dB(μ V) and L_h the height correction factor (for the effective height) given in meters or dB(m). The height correction factor L_h in dB(m) and effective height of the rod h_e in meters are calculated using (1.12) and (1.13), respectively, where λ denotes the wavelength of the signal (*i.e.*, $\lambda=c/f$), where c denoted the speed of light ($2.998 \cdot 10^8$ m/s), f the frequency of the signal and h the actual height (length) of the rod in meters. The capacitance C_a of dummy capacitor (*i.e.*, self-capacitance of the rod above infinite ground plane) is calculated using (1.15) (in pF), where a denotes the average radius of the rod in meters.

$$AAF = \frac{E}{V_m} = \frac{V_D}{V_L} \cdot \frac{1}{h_e}, \text{ in m}^{-1} \quad (1.10)$$

$$AF = V_D - V_L - L_h, \quad (1.11)$$

$$L_h = 20 \cdot \log(h_e), \quad (1.12)$$

$$h_e = \frac{\lambda}{2 \cdot \pi} \tan \frac{\pi \cdot h}{\lambda}, \quad (1.13)$$

$$L_h = 20 \cdot \log \left(h_e + \frac{h_b}{2} \right), \quad (1.14)$$

$$C_a = \frac{55.6 \cdot h}{\ln\left(\frac{h}{a}\right) - 1} \cdot \frac{\tan\left(\frac{2 \cdot \pi \cdot h}{\lambda}\right)}{\frac{2 \cdot \pi \cdot h}{\lambda}} \tag{1.15}$$

The measuring setup based on VNA is shown in Fig. 1-5. The 10 dB attenuators were connected to Port 1 and 2 of the VNA, respectively, to reduce mismatch losses. The calibration adapter was connected to the input port of the antenna. In the first step, the thru measurement was performed, i.e., the Ports 1 and 2 of the VNA were connected to T-connector which was connected to the input port of the calibration adapter, The output of the monopole antenna was terminated by 50 Ω BNC load. In the second step, the port 2 of the VNA was re-connected to the output of the monopole antenna, while the remaining input of the T-connector was terminated by the 50 Ω BNC load. With this setup the attenuation was measured (V_D-V_L) and used in (1.11) to calculate the AF. Additionally, a -5 dB was subtracted from the attenuation measurements as specified in manufacturers specifications, since the calibration adapter also include some resistive elements.

Fig. 1-5 A measuring set-up for monopole antenna calibration with ECSM method with VNA

1.6.3.2 Equipment

The equipment that was used during the calibration is listed in Tab. 1-16 and the uncertainty calculation example for 1 MHz is given in Tab. 1-17.

Tab. 1-16 Standards used in measurements.

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No.
VNA	Agilent	E5061B	MY49304497
50 Ω termination	Huber&Suhner	6506.01.A	17H
10 dB attenuator	HP	8492A	8593
10 dB attenuator	HP	8491B	15778
Calibration Fixture	ETS-Lindgren	3301CAL-B?	00206934

Tab. 1-17 Calculation example and uncertainty budget

ΔV	-12,56 dB	$AF = (\Delta V + \delta\Delta V_{meas} + \delta\Delta V_{D,MM} - \delta\Delta V_{L,MM} - \delta V_{L,Ca} - \delta V_{L,amp}) - (L_h + \delta L_{L,h})$
L_h	-6,021 dB	
f	1000 kHz	
λ	299,8 m	
d	5 mm	
l	104 cm	
C_a	11,50 pF	
C_a'	12,59 pF	

Quantity X_i	Estimate x_i	Standard uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Probability distribution	Div.	Sensitivity coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u_i(y)$	Effective degr. Of freedom ν_i
ΔV	-12,56 dB	0,03 dB	normal	2	1 /	0,03 dB	5
$\delta V_{D,MM}$	0 dB	0,19 dB	U-shaped	1,41	1 /	0,19 dB	1E+99
$\delta V_{L,MM}$	0 dB	0,19 dB	U-shaped	1,41	1 /	0,19 dB	1E+99
$L_{L,h}$	-5,680 dB	0,20 dB	rectengular	1,73	1 /	0,20 dB	5
$\delta V_{L,Ca}$	0 dB	0,45 dB	rectengular	1,73	1 /	0,45 dB	15
$\delta V_{L,amp}$	0 dB	0 dB	normal	1	1 /	0 dB	1E+99
AF	-1,88 dB	Calculated uncertainty:				0,56 dB	32
		Expanded uncertainty of measurement:				1,21 dB	

1.6.3.3 Measurement results

Measurements results are shown in Tab. 1-18. The ambient temperature and relative humidity during the calibration were $23\text{ °C} \pm 2\text{ °C}$ and $50\% \pm 20\%$, respectively.

Tab. 1-18 Measurement results

Frequency (MHz)	AF dB (1/m)	Unc. (dB) (k=2)	Frequency (MHz)	AF dB (1/m)	Unc. (dB) (k=2)
0.009	-1.64	1.21	4	-1.92	1.20
0.01	-1.65	1.20	5	-1.89	1.18
0.02	-1.65	1.21	6	-1.87	1.17
0.03	-1.64	1.20	7	-1.86	1.15
0.04	-1.69	1.21	8	-1.82	1.14
0.05	-1.70	1.21	9	-1.78	1.11
0.06	-1.69	1.21	10	-1.74	1.09
0.07	-1.71	1.21	11	-1.70	1.06
0.08	-1.72	1.21	12	-1.62	1.02
0.09	-1.76	1.21	13	-1.57	1.00
0.10	-1.74	1.21	14	-1.53	0.96
0.11	-1.74	1.20	15	-1.46	0.92
0.12	-1.75	1.21	16	-1.39	0.89
0.13	-1.73	1.21	17	-1.33	0.85
0.14	-1.75	1.21	18	-1.26	0.82

0.15	-1.76	1.21	19	-1.18	0.78
0.2	-1.77	1.21	20	-1.10	0.75
0.3	-1.79	1.22	21	-1.03	0.73
0.4	-1.82	1.20	22	-0.97	0.71
0.5	-1.83	1.21	23	-0.89	0.69
0.6	-1.86	1.21	24	-0.79	0.69
0.7	-1.86	1.21	25	-0.67	0.69
0.8	-1.87	1.21	26	-0.64	0.71
0.9	-1.88	1.21	27	-0.56	0.76
1	-1.88	1.21	28	-0.46	0.80
2	-1.89	1.20	29	-0.38	0.86
3	-1.91	1.21	30	-0.29	1.20

1.7 Analysis of results

The measured AF from TÜBİTAK (green line), RISE (red line) and SIQ (blue line) are gathered in Fig. 1-6. The corresponding extended measuring uncertainties ($k = 2$) are shown with dashed lines. There is an excellent agreement between TUBITAK and SIQ. The AF measured by RISE are slightly higher, but the values are still well within the measurement uncertainty.

Fig. 1-6 The measured results from TUBITAK, RISE and SIQ

Afterwards, the weighed mean of AF and standard uncertainty were calculated using (1.16) and (1.17), respectively. The results are shown in Fig. 1-7 (note, the uncertainty correspond to standard measuring uncertainties with $k = 1$) and in Tab. 1-19.

$$y = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i u^{-2}(x_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N u^{-2}(x_i)} \quad (1.16)$$

$$u(y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N u^{-2}(x_i)}} \quad (1.17)$$

Tab. 1-19 Weighed mean of AF (y) and corresponding uncertainty u(y).

Frequency (MHz)	y (dB (1/m))	u(y) (dB) (k=1)	Frequency (MHz)	y (dB (1/m))	u(y) (dB) (k=1)
0.009	-1.603	0.279	4	-1.891	0.279
0.01	-1.615	0.279	5	-1.874	0.278
0.02	-1.638	0.279	6	-1.854	0.277
0.03	-1.633	0.279	7	-1.829	0.276
0.04	-1.674	0.279	8	-1.794	0.276
0.05	-1.696	0.279	9	-1.754	0.274
0.06	-1.700	0.279	10	-1.711	0.273
0.07	-1.710	0.279	11	-1.662	0.271
0.08	-1.713	0.279	12	-1.600	0.268
0.09	-1.728	0.279	13	-1.547	0.267
0.1	-1.726	0.279	14	-1.492	0.264
0.11	-1.731	0.279	15	-1.422	0.261
0.12	-1.734	0.279	16	-1.357	0.258
0.13	-1.732	0.279	17	-1.289	0.254
0.14	-1.742	0.279	18	-1.217	0.251
0.15	-1.744	0.279	19	-1.139	0.246
0.2	-1.762	0.279	20	-1.061	0.242
0.3	-1.782	0.280	21	-0.985	0.240
0.4	-1.805	0.279	22	-0.912	0.237
0.5	-1.823	0.279	23	-0.827	0.234
0.6	-1.836	0.279	24	-0.736	0.234
0.7	-1.844	0.279	25	-0.636	0.234
0.8	-1.854	0.279	26	-0.567	0.237
0.9	-1.861	0.279	27	-0.479	0.244
1	-1.864	0.279	28	-0.379	0.249
2	-1.890	0.279	29	-0.284	0.255
3	-1.896	0.279	30	-0.176	0.279

Fig. 1-7 The weighted mean of AF and standard uncertainty with $k=1$

Afterwards, the consistency of the results χ_{obs} was calculated using (1.18). Afterwards, the *Chi-test* has been performed using the CHIDIST function in Excel. The consistency check is considered fails if (1.19) is satisfied. In our case the minimum value that was observed equals to 0.83 therefore no result (laboratory) needs to be excluded from the calculation. Finally, the degree of equivalence E_n has been calculated for each participating laboratory using (1.20). The results are gathered in Tab. 1-20. The E_n value should be within $-1.0 < E_n < +1.0$ interval. The maximal absolute value for E_n for SIQ (0.13) and TUBITAK (0.17). On contrary the E_n starts increasing above 20 MHz in the case of the RISE measurements and approaches to 0.28 at 30 MHz. Nevertheless, all results are in excellent agreement.

$$\chi_{obs}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(x_i - y)^2}{u^2(x_i)} \quad (1.18)$$

$$Pr\{\chi^2(v) > \chi_{obs}^2\} < 5\%, \quad (1.19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_n &= \frac{\Delta x_i}{U(\Delta x_i)} \\ \Delta x_i &= x_i - y \\ U(\Delta x_i) &= 2 \cdot u(\Delta x_i) \\ u^2(\Delta x_i) &= u^2(x_i) - u^2(y) \end{aligned} \quad (1.20)$$

Tab. 1-20 The degree of equivalence E_n for TÜBİTAK, RISE and SIQ.

Frequency (MHz)	E_n TÜBİTAK	E_n RISE	E_n SIQ
0.009	0.01	0.04	0.03
0.01	0.01	0.04	0.03
0.02	0.04	0.06	0.01
0.03	0.05	0.07	0.01
0.04	0.05	0.07	0.01
0.05	0.05	0.06	0.00
0.06	0.06	0.06	0.01
0.07	0.06	0.07	0.00
0.08	0.05	0.07	0.01
0.09	0.04	0.07	0.03
0.1	0.05	0.07	0.01
0.11	0.06	0.07	0.01
0.12	0.05	0.07	0.01
0.13	0.06	0.06	0.00
0.14	0.06	0.07	0.01
0.15	0.05	0.07	0.01
0.2	0.06	0.07	0.01
0.3	0.06	0.07	0.01
0.4	0.05	0.07	0.01
0.5	0.05	0.07	0.01
0.6	0.05	0.07	0.02
0.7	0.05	0.07	0.01
0.8	0.05	0.07	0.01
0.9	0.06	0.08	0.02
1	0.05	0.07	0.01
2	0.06	0.07	0.00
3	0.05	0.07	0.01
4	0.04	0.07	0.03
5	0.05	0.07	0.01
6	0.05	0.07	0.01
7	0.04	0.08	0.03
8	0.05	0.08	0.02
9	0.05	0.08	0.02
10	0.06	0.09	0.03
11	0.05	0.10	0.04
12	0.06	0.09	0.02
13	0.06	0.10	0.03
14	0.05	0.11	0.04
15	0.05	0.11	0.05
16	0.06	0.12	0.04
17	0.06	0.13	0.06
18	0.06	0.14	0.06
19	0.05	0.14	0.06
20	0.07	0.16	0.06
21	0.06	0.17	0.08
22	0.05	0.19	0.10
23	0.04	0.20	0.12
24	0.06	0.20	0.10
25	0.09	0.20	0.06
26	0.06	0.23	0.13

27	0.07	0.25	0.13
28	0.09	0.25	0.12
29	0.10	0.27	0.13
30	0.17	0.28	0.10

Finally, the *Degrees of equivalence (DoE)* and corresponding uncertainties have been calculated for each participating laboratory using (1.20). The results are gathered in Tab. 1-21. Additionally, the results are shown in Fig. 1-8 to Fig. 1-61 for each measured frequency.

Tab. 1-21 The *Degrees of equivalence (DoE)* and corresponding uncertainties for TÜBİTAK, RISE and SIQ.

Frequency (MHz)	TÜBİTAK		RISE		SIQ	
	D_i	$U(D_i)$	D_i	$U(D_i)$	D_i	$U(D_i)$
0.009	-0.007	0.495	0.043	0.984	-0.037	1.164
0.01	-0.005	0.496	0.039	0.985	-0.035	1.152
0.02	-0.022	0.495	0.057	0.984	-0.012	1.164
0.03	-0.027	0.496	0.066	0.985	-0.007	1.152
0.04	-0.026	0.495	0.070	0.984	-0.016	1.164
0.05	-0.024	0.495	0.056	0.984	-0.004	1.164
0.06	-0.030	0.495	0.058	0.984	0.010	1.164
0.07	-0.030	0.495	0.066	0.984	0.000	1.164
0.08	-0.027	0.495	0.065	0.984	-0.007	1.164
0.09	-0.022	0.495	0.073	0.984	-0.032	1.164
0.1	-0.024	0.495	0.066	0.984	-0.014	1.164
0.11	-0.029	0.496	0.073	0.985	-0.009	1.152
0.12	-0.026	0.495	0.070	0.984	-0.016	1.164
0.13	-0.028	0.495	0.061	0.984	0.002	1.164
0.14	-0.028	0.495	0.070	0.984	-0.008	1.164
0.15	-0.026	0.495	0.072	0.984	-0.016	1.164
0.2	-0.028	0.495	0.069	0.984	-0.008	1.164
0.3	-0.028	0.494	0.067	0.984	-0.008	1.177
0.4	-0.025	0.496	0.066	0.985	-0.015	1.152
0.5	-0.027	0.495	0.065	0.984	-0.007	1.164
0.6	-0.024	0.495	0.074	0.984	-0.024	1.164
0.7	-0.026	0.495	0.072	0.984	-0.016	1.164
0.8	-0.026	0.495	0.071	0.984	-0.016	1.164
0.9	-0.029	0.495	0.078	0.984	-0.019	1.164
1	-0.026	0.495	0.072	0.984	-0.016	1.164
2	-0.030	0.496	0.067	0.985	0.000	1.152
3	-0.024	0.495	0.064	0.984	-0.014	1.164
4	-0.019	0.496	0.067	0.985	-0.029	1.152
5	-0.026	0.498	0.072	0.986	-0.016	1.127
6	-0.026	0.499	0.072	0.987	-0.016	1.115
7	-0.021	0.502	0.075	0.988	-0.031	1.091
8	-0.026	0.503	0.080	0.988	-0.026	1.078
9	-0.026	0.506	0.081	0.990	-0.026	1.042
10	-0.029	0.509	0.093	0.992	-0.029	1.017
11	-0.028	0.513	0.101	0.994	-0.038	0.981
12	-0.030	0.518	0.090	0.997	-0.020	0.932
13	-0.033	0.521	0.102	0.998	-0.023	0.908
14	-0.028	0.528	0.111	1.002	-0.038	0.860

15	-0.028	0.534	0.112	1.005	-0.038	0.812
16	-0.033	0.539	0.123	1.008	-0.033	0.776
17	-0.031	0.547	0.135	1.012	-0.041	0.728
18	-0.033	0.553	0.145	1.016	-0.043	0.692
19	-0.031	0.561	0.145	1.021	-0.041	0.645
20	-0.039	0.568	0.166	1.024	-0.039	0.610
21	-0.035	0.572	0.177	1.027	-0.045	0.586
22	-0.028	0.577	0.193	1.030	-0.058	0.563
23	-0.023	0.582	0.201	1.032	-0.063	0.540
24	-0.034	0.582	0.205	1.032	-0.054	0.540
25	-0.054	0.582	0.203	1.032	-0.034	0.540
26	-0.033	0.577	0.238	1.030	-0.073	0.563
27	-0.041	0.565	0.253	1.023	-0.081	0.621
28	-0.051	0.557	0.258	1.018	-0.081	0.669
29	-0.056	0.545	0.272	1.011	-0.096	0.740
30	-0.084	0.496	0.275	0.985	-0.114	1.152

Fig. 1-8 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 9 kHz

Fig. 1-9 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 10 kHz

Fig. 1-10 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 20 kHz

Fig. 1-11 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 30 kHz

Fig. 1-12 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 40 kHz

Fig. 1-13 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 50 kHz

Fig. 1-14 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 60 kHz

Fig. 1-15 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 70 kHz

Fig. 1-16 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 80 kHz

Fig. 1-17 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 90 kHz

Fig. 1-18 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 100 kHz

Fig. 1-19 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 110 kHz

Fig. 1-20 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 120 kHz

Fig. 1-21 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 130 kHz

Fig. 1-22 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 140 kHz

Fig. 1-23 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 150 kHz

Fig. 1-24 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 200 kHz

Fig. 1-25 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 300 kHz

Fig. 1-26 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 400 kHz

Fig. 1-27 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 500 kHz

Fig. 1-28 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 600 kHz

Fig. 1-29 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 700 kHz

Fig. 1-30 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 800 kHz

Fig. 1-31 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 900 kHz

Fig. 1-32 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 1 MHz

Fig. 1-33 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 2 MHz

Fig. 1-34 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 3 MHz

Fig. 1-35 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 4 MHz

Fig. 1-36 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 5 MHz

Fig. 1-37 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 6 MHz

Fig. 1-38 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 7 MHz

Fig. 1-39 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 8 MHz

Fig. 1-40 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 9 MHz

Fig. 1-41 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 10 MHz

Fig. 1-42 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 11 MHz

Fig. 1-43 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 12 MHz

Fig. 1-44 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 13 MHz

Fig. 1-45 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 14 MHz

Fig. 1-46 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 15 MHz

Fig. 1-47 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 16 MHz

Fig. 1-48 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 17 MHz

Fig. 1-49 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 18 MHz

Fig. 1-50 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 19 MHz

Fig. 1-51 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 20 MHz

Fig. 1-52 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 21 MHz

Fig. 1-53 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 22 MHz

Fig. 1-54 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 23 MHz

Fig. 1-55 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 24 MHz

Fig. 1-56 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 25 MHz

Fig. 1-57 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 26 MHz

Fig. 1-58 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 27 MHz

Fig. 1-59 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 28 MHz

Fig. 1-60 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 29 MHz

Fig. 1-61 Degrees of equivalence for monopole antenna ETS-Lindgren 3301C at 30 MHz

1.8 Annex A1

Measurement Report for Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II (22RPT04 RF&Microwave2)

Each participant should provide the following information, Tables A1.1-A1.5.

Table A1.1: Participant information

Institute Name:	
Contact Person:	
Telephone No.:	
E-mail:	
Address:	

Table A1.2: Measurement date

Measurement Dates –
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Table A1.3: Standards used in measurements.

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No.

Table A1.4: Measurement results

Frequency	Antenna Factor dB (1/m)	Measurement Uncertainty (dB) ($k=2$)	Ambient Temperature (°C)	Ambient Humidity (%RH)
9 kHz				
...				
...				
...				
30 (50) MHz				

Table A1.5: Calculation example and uncertainty budget

Uncertainty budget at the frequency of Hz						
source of uncertainty	type (A or B)	expected value x_i	probability distribution	k -factor	sens. Coeff. c_i	standard uncertainty contribution $u(x_i)$
measured value						
combined unc.						
expanded unc. ($k=2$)						

1.9 Annex B1

DELIVERY NOTE – FOR TRANSPORTATION OF THE TRAVELLING STANDARD

A	TRAVELLING STANDARD:	
	Monopole antenna:	
	Manufacturer:	ETS-Lindgren
	Model:	model 3301C
	Serial Number:	00152392
	ADDITIONAL EQUIPMENT:	
	Manufacturer:	
	Model:	
	Serial number:	
	Power Meter // Manufacturer:	
	Model:	
	Serial number:	
	OTHER MISCELLANEOUS MATERIAL:	
	- Cables	--
	- Protective package and wrapping	Yes
	- Technical Manual	No
	- Technical Protocol of comparison	No
	COLOUR OF THE SHOCKWATCH®	
	INDICATION OF THE TILTWATCH PLUS®	Not applicable
B	DELIVERING LABORATORY:	
	Name of person responsible for the delivery:	Observations:
	Signature and stamp:	
C	LABORATORY RECEIVING THE TRAVELLING STANDARD:	
	Name of person receiving the equipment:	Observations:
	Signature and stamp:	
DATE OF DELIVERY:		

2. BILATERAL COMPARISON OF OPEN AREA TEST SITE ANTENNA MEASUREMENTS

Partners: TÜBİTAK UME, RISE

January 2025

2.1 Introduction

A bilateral comparison was organized between TÜBİTAK UME and RISE in the field of 30 MHz - 1 GHz antenna factor measurements at Open Area Test Site (OATS) in accordance with CISPR 16-1-6 [2.7] standard site method (SSM). The comparison was performed within the scope of the Development of RF Microwave Metrology Capability II (22RPT04 RF Microwave 2).

Biconical and log-periodic antennas are widely utilized in the measurement of electric field component of the electromagnetic waves radiated from broadcasting in TV and radio communications and in electromagnetic compatibility/interference (EMC/EMI) testing in accordance with the commercial and military standards in the frequency range of 30 MHz – 1 GHz. Therefore, the calibration of biconical and log-periodic antennas are of fundamental importance for the traceability of the free space antenna factor measurements. This kind of antennas must be calibrated by National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) or accredited calibration laboratories in accordance with international standards such as CISPR 16-1-6 [2.7].

The comparison was conducted in accordance with the Technical Protocol of “Bilateral Comparison of Open Area Test Site Antenna Measurements Between TÜRKİYE TÜBİTAK UME and SWEDEN RISE, given in Appendix B2, which was prepared by the TÜBİTAK UME and approved by RISE, SWEDEN.

2.2 Organisation of the comparison

2.2.1 Pilot institute

This comparison was piloted by TÜBİTAK UME. The travelling standards were provided by TÜBİTAK UME. TÜBİTAK UME was responsible for monitoring the performance of travelling standards during the circulation and for the evaluation and reporting of the comparison results.

2.2.2 Participating institutes

The participating institutes are listed in Tab. 2-1

Tab. 2-1 List of participants

Acronym of Institute	Country	Contact Person	Shipping Address
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	Mehmet Çınar mehmet.cinar@tubitak.gov.tr Tel: +90 262 679 50 00	TÜBİTAK Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü (UME) TÜBİTAK Gebze Yerleşkesi Barış Mah. Dr. Zeki Acar Cad. No:1 41470 Gebze-Kocaeli, Türkiye
RISE	Sweden	Mats Cedheim mats.cedheim@ri.se Tel: +46 10 516 60 86	Research Institutes of SWEDEN (RISE) Mats Cedheim/Hus 15 Brinellgatan 4, 504 62 Borås Sweden

2.2.3 Comparison schedule

The comparison was organized in a single loop of two laboratories to allow close monitoring of the behaviour of the travelling standards. Participants had about 22 weeks to carry out the measurements and transportation. A delay, compared to the planned schedule, occurred mainly due to the delay of the other comparisons at scope of the Development of RF Microwave Metrology Capability II (22RPT04 RF Microwave 2). The actual time schedule is given in Tab. 2-2.

Tab. 2-2 The actual time schedule for the comparison

Institute	Country	Measurement Dates
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	24.04.2024 – 25.04.2024
RISE	Sweden	17.06.2024 – 19.06.2024
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	08.10.2024 – 09.10.2024

2.3 Travelling standards

2.3.1 Description of the Standard

The travelling standards were supplied by TÜBİTAK UME. These standards were chosen for their high accuracy and stability over time. The photos and the general specifications of the travelling standards are presented in Fig. 2-1 and Tab. 2-3, respectively.

Fig. 2-1 The photo of the travelling standards (a) Biconical antenna (b) Log Periodic antenna

Tab. 2-3 General specifications of the travelling standards

Name	Manufacturer	Model	Serial Number	Frequency Range
Biconical antenna	Schaffner	VBA6106A	1298	30 MHz - 300 MHz
Log Periodic antenna	Schwarzbeck	VUSLP 9111B	00509	200 MHz - 1 GHz

2.3.2 Measured Quantities and Conditions of the Measurement

The comparison will be performed by measuring the biconical and log periodic antennas at 10 meter distance and horizontal polarization. The comparison frequencies are 30 MHz, 60 MHz, 100 MHz, 200 MHz, 300 MHz for the biconical antenna and, 200 MHz, 300 MHz, 500 MHz, 800 MHz and 1000 MHz for the log periodic

antenna, respectively (Tab. 2-4). The antenna factors must be measured for each frequency. The antenna factor measurements must be performed in accordance with CISPR 16-1-6 [2.7] standard site method (SSM). Also log periodic antenna must be measured from the ref. point and biconical antenna must be measured of the phase centre for 10 m distance. Photos of the log periodic antenna ref. point and biconical antenna phase centre are presented in Fig. 2-2.

Fig. 2-2 The photos of the antennas measurement point for 10 meters measurements (a) Log periodic antenna ref.point (b) Biconical antenna phase centre

Tab. 2-4 Measurement points & conditions

Relevant travelling Standard	Measurement frequencies (MHz)	Polarization	Measurement distance (Meter)	Height (Meter)
Biconical antenna	30	Horizontal	10	Transmitter Antenna: 2 meters Receive Antenna: 1 meter - 4 meters Scan
	60			
	100			
	200			
	300			
Log periodic antenna	200	Horizontal	10	Transmitter Antenna: 2 meters Receive Antenna: 1 meter - 4 meters Scan
	300			
	500			
	800			
	1000			

2.4 Methods of Measurement

The measurements were performed according to participants' measurement procedure. The detailed measurement methods used by the participants were given in the comparison reports of the participants in Annex A2.

2.5 Results of the Participating Institutes

The measurement results of the participating institutes (x_i) and their standard uncertainties ($u(x_i)$) are presented for each frequency in Tab. 2-5. TÜBİTAK UME measurements specified in Tab. 2-2 are the average of the measurements taken before the comparison and after the RISE measurements.

Tab. 2-5 Results of the participating institutes

Relevant Travelling Standard	Frequency (MHz)	Participating Institute	Correction Factor (dB)	Standard Uncertainty (k=2) (dB)	
Biconical antenna	30	TÜBİTAK UME	18.4	0.67	
		RISE	18.51	1.00	
	60	TÜBİTAK UME	6.9	0.67	
		RISE	7.21	1.00	
	100	TÜBİTAK UME	11.1	0.67	
		RISE	11.10	1.00	
	200	TÜBİTAK UME	15.1	0.67	
		RISE	15.33	1.00	
	300	TÜBİTAK UME	19.0	0.67	
		RISE	19.33	1.00	
	Log periodic antenna	200	TÜBİTAK UME	11.4	0.80
			RISE	11.49	1.00
300		TÜBİTAK UME	13.7	0.80	
		RISE	13.19	1.00	
500		TÜBİTAK UME	17.7	0.80	
		RISE	17.43	1.00	

	800	TÜBİTAK UME	20.9	0.80
		RISE	20.84	1.00
	1000	TÜBİTAK UME	22.5	0.80
		RISE	21.83	1.00

2.6 Calculation of Comparison Reference Values and associated uncertainties

The Comparison Reference Value (CRV) is calculated separately for each parameter. The CRV is considered as an estimation of the measurand according to the measurements provided by the participating laboratories. This estimation, x_{ref} , is determined as a weighted mean of the provided results where the weights are the inverse values of the squares of the associated standard uncertainties [2.2].

The weighted mean x_{ref} of the data set and the associated expanded uncertainty $U(x_{ref})$ are obtained from

$$x_{ref} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{U^2(x_i)}} \quad (2.1)$$

$$U^2(x_{ref}) = 1 / \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{U^2(x_i)} \quad (2.2)$$

Tab. 2-6 Comparison reference values and expanded uncertainties for all measurements

Relevant Travelling Standard	Frequency (MHz)	x_{ref} (dB)	$U(x_{ref})$ (dB)
Biconical antenna	30	18.434	0.289
	60	6.996	
	100	11.100	
	200	15.171	
	300	19.102	
Log periodic antenna	200	11.435	0.326
	300	13.506	

	500	17.596	
	800	20.877	
	1000	22.246	

2.7 Calculation of degrees of equivalence

The results of the comparison are reported as the degrees of equivalence (DoE) and the CRV. The degrees of equivalence of each participant are calculated as:

$$D_i = x_i - x_{ref} \quad (2.3)$$

Where x_i is the results of the participant and x_{ref} is the CRV.

The expanded uncertainty of the degree of equivalence for a participant's result $U(D_i)$ is calculated as:

$$U^2(D_i) = U^2(x_i) - U^2(x_{ref}) \quad (2.4)$$

For each participant's result, the normalized error (E_n) is calculated as:

$$E_n = \frac{|D_i|}{U(D_i)} \quad (2.5)$$

The participant results are regarded as satisfactory if $E_n \leq 1$.

Tab. 2-7 The degrees of equivalence (D_i), its uncertainties ($U(D_i)$) and E_n values (biconical antenna)

Relevant Travelling Standard	Frequency (MHz)	Participating Institute	D_i (dB)	$U(D_i)$ (dB)	E_n
Biconical antenna	30	TÜBİTAK UME	-0.034	0.382	0.09
		RISE	0.076	0.880	0.09
	60	TÜBİTAK UME	-0.096	0.382	0.25
		RISE	0.214	0.880	0.24
	100	TÜBİTAK UME	0.000	0.382	0.00
		RISE	0.000	0.880	0.00
	200	TÜBİTAK UME	-0.071	0.382	0.19

		RISE	0.159	0.880	0.18
	300	TÜBİTAK UME	-0.102	0.382	0.27
		RISE	0.228	0.880	0.26

Tab. 2-8 The degrees of equivalence (D_i), its uncertainties ($U(D_i)$) and E_n values (log-periodic antenna)

Relevant Travelling Standard	Frequency (MHz)	Participating Institute	D_i (dB)	$U(D_i)$ (dB)	E_n
Log periodic antenna	200	TÜBİTAK UME	-0.035	0.517	0.07
		RISE	0.055	0.825	0.07
	300	TÜBİTAK UME	0.194	0.517	0.38
		RISE	-0.316	0.825	0.38
	500	TÜBİTAK UME	0.104	0.517	0.20
		RISE	-0.166	0.825	0.20
	800	TÜBİTAK UME	0.023	0.517	0.04
		RISE	-0.037	0.825	0.04
	1000	TÜBİTAK UME	0.254	0.517	0.49
		RISE	-0.416	0.825	0.50

Fig. 2-3 Degrees of equivalence for biconical antenna 30 MHz

Fig. 2-4 Degrees of equivalence for biconical antenna 60 MHz

Fig. 2-5 Degrees of equivalence for biconical antenna 100 MHz

Fig. 2-6 Degrees of equivalence for biconical antenna 200 MHz

Fig. 2-7 Degrees of equivalence for biconical antenna 300 MHz

Fig. 2-8 Degrees of equivalence for log periodic antenna 200 MHz

Fig. 2-9 Degrees of equivalence for log periodic antenna 300 MHz

Fig. 2-10 Degrees of equivalence for log periodic antenna 500 MHz

Fig. 2-11 Degrees of equivalence for log periodic antenna 800 MHz

Fig. 2-12 Degrees of equivalence for log periodic antenna 1000 MHz

2.8 Conclusion

The comparison has been conducted between TÜBİTAK UME and RISE. As traveling standard, two antennas were used. They have low dependence on ambient parameters and very stable behavior. The travelling standards were circulated without major problem from May 2024 to September 2024.

The CRV was determined by using the weighted mean of the participants measurement results. In the CRV calculations, the values used in the comparison report were obtained by converting the decibel values to linear values.

The comparison results showed a good agreement between TÜBİTAK UME and RISE both for the biconical antenna (30 MHz - 300 MHz) and log periodic antenna (200 MHz - 1 GHz) within the stated uncertainties. En values for each participant for all measurement points satisfy Equation (2.5).

This comparison results will lead participants to improve their calibration setups and revise their uncertainty budgets.

2.9 References

- [2.1] J. Randa: "Update to proposal for KCRV & degree of equivalence for GTRF key comparisons", NIST, February 2005.
- [2.2] W. Bich, M. Cox, T. Estler, L. Nielsen, W. Woeger, "*Proposed guidelines for the evaluation of key comparison data*", CCAUV/02-36, April 2002.
- [2.3] Cox M. G.: The Evaluation of Key Comparison Data. *Metrology* **39**, pp. 589-595, 2002.
- [2.4] JCGM 100:2008 *Evaluation of measurement data. – Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement*. Working Group 1 of the Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, Sept. 2008
- [2.5] EA-4/02 M:2022 *Evaluation of the Uncertainty of Measurement in calibration*. European Accreditation, April 2022
- [2.6] Final Report EURAMET.EM-S43 (EURAMET Project no: 1492), September 2022.
- [2.7] CISPR 16-1-6, "*Radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus - EMC Antenna calibration*", IEC, Edition 1.1, 2017-1

2.10 Measurement reports for each participant

2.10.1 TÜBİTAK UME

2.10.1.1 Participant Information

Institute Name	TÜBİTAK UME
Contact Person	Mehmet Çınar, Serdar Büyük, Ahmet Emre Karakoyunlu
Telephone No	+90 262 679 50 00
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Address	TÜBİTAK Gebze Yerleşkesi, Barış Mah. Dr. Zeki Acar Cad. No:1 41470 Gebze-Kocaeli, Türkiye

2.10.1.2 Measurement Date

Measurement Dates	08.10.2024 – 09.10.2024
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2.10.1.3 References Used In Measurement

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No
Antenna Calibration Site	TÜBİTAK UME	60 m x 30 m	001
Network Analyzer	Keysight	E5061B	MY49407095
10 dB Coaxial Fixed Attenuator	Keysight	8491B	-
10 dB Coaxial Fixed Attenuator	Keysight	8491B	-
Biconical Antenna	Emco	3110B	9607-2572
Biconical Antenna	Rohde@Schwarz	HK116	100467
Log Periodic Antenna	Schwarzbeck	VUSLP 9111B	00510
Log Periodic Antenna	Schaffner	UPA6109	1097

2.10.1.4 Measurement Procedure

The antenna measurements were performed in horizontal polarization in accordance with the standard site method (SSM) [1], [2] at open field antenna calibration site using coaxial line of which impedance is equal to 50 Ohm and a network analyzer.

The TÜBİTAK UME open field antenna calibration site comprises a 60 meters x 30 meters metal ground plane, of which flatness is within ± 5 mm over %95 of its surface area (Fig. 2-13). The flatness measurements were performed using a laser tracker at 1891 points. Also the antenna calibration site SIL measurements were certified by CHINA NIM. The site insertion loss (SIL) measurements were carried out using CHINA NIM calculable dipole antennas. Also theoretical SIL values were calculated with the software AntCalculator, which is developed by NIM based on NEC2++.

Fig. 2-13 60 meters x 30 meters antenna calibration site

Three antennas are required for the SSM (Fig. 2-14). Therefore, apart from the travel standards, two more biconical antennas and two more log periodic antennas were provided by TUBITAK UME. The antennas measurements were carried out at a distance of 10 meters (Fig. 2-15). The distance between the antennas was measured from the phase center for biconical antennas and from the mid-point for log periodic antennas. Also the correction factors in section C.6.2 of the CISPR 16-1-6 [1] standard were not applied for biconical antennas.

Fig. 2-14 Three site attenuation measurements using three different antennas in pairs

Fig. 2-15 Measurement set-up for SSM at calibration site with a metal ground plane

2.10.1.5 References

- [1] CISPR 16-1-6, Edition 1.1 (2017), Specification for radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus and methods - Part 1-6: Radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus - EMC antenna calibration.
- [2] ANSI C63.5 (2017), American National Standard for Electromagnetic Compatibility – Radiated Emission Measurements in Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) Control – Calibration of Antennas (9 kHz to 40 GHz).

2.10.1.6 Measurement Results

Measurement results were given in Tab. 2-9.

Tab. 2-9 Measurement results for 10 meter measurement distance and horizontal polarization

Relevant travelling Standard	Frequency (MHz)	Antenna Factor dB(1/m)	Measurement Uncertainty (dB) (k=2)	Ambient Temperature (°C)	Ambient Humidity (%rh)
Biconical antenna	30	18.4	0,67	Control room 22 ± 2 Site 30 ± 5	45 ± 15
	60	6.9			
	100	11.1			
	200	15.1			
	300	19.0			

Log periodic antenna	200	11.4	0,80		
	300	13.7			
	500	17.7			
	800	20.9			
	1000	22.5			

2.10.1.7 Detailed Uncertainty Budgets

Tab. 2-10 Biconical antenna measurements

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 30 MHz to 300 MHz for biconical antenna measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (dB)
Receiver reading accuracy after direct connection of cables	B	0,070	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,035
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna2-1	B	0,200	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,100
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna3-1	B	0,190	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,095
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna3-2	B	0,200	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,100
Generator- receiver (direct connection mismatch with an adapter)	B	0,053	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0,866	0,032
Generator-antenna mismatch	B	0,086	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0,866	0,053
Antenna-receiver mismatch	B	0,079	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0,866	0,048
Effect of site and masts	B	0,450	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,225
Antenna height positioning	B	0,226	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,113

Antenna distance positioning	B	0,071	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,035
Antenna misalignment	B	0,094	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,047
Cable attenuation variation due to cable flexing or temperature fluctuation	B	0,040	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,020
Ambient noise	B	0,100	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,050
Repeatability	A	0,070	Normal	1	1	0,070
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0,67

Tab. 2-11 Log periodic antenna measurements

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 200 MHz to 1000 MHz for log periodic antenna measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (dB)
Receiver reading accuracy after direct connection of cables	B	0,080	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,040
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna2-1	B	0,150	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,075
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna3-1	B	0,150	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,075
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna3-2	B	0,140	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,070
Generator- receiver (direct connection mismatch with an adapter)	B	0,205	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0,866	0,126
Generator-antenna mismatch	B	0,185	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0,866	0,113
Antenna-receiver mismatch	B	0,180	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0,866	0,110
Effect of site and masts	B	0,570	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,285
Antenna height positioning	B	0,092	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,046

Antenna distance positioning	B	0,074	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,037
Antenna misalignment	B	0,124	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,062
Cable attenuation variation due to cable flexing or temperature fluctuation	B	0,040	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,020
Ambient noise	B	0,100	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,050
Effect of the phase center	B	0,180	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,090
Repeatability	A	0,040	Normal	1	1	0,040
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0,80

2.10.2 RISE

2.10.2.1 Participant Information

Institute Name:	RISE
Contact Person:	Mats Cedheim
Telephone No.:	+46 10 516 60 86
E-mail:	Mats.cedheim@ri.se
Address:	Brinellgatan 4, 504 62 Boras, Sweden

2.10.2.2 Measurement Date

Measurement Dates17.06.2024.... – 19.06.2024.....
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2.10.2.3 References Used In Measurement

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No
Network Analyzer	Rohde&Schwarz	ZNB-8	103544
Pre-amplifier	Hewlett-Packard	HP 8447D	2944A08401
10 dB attenuator	Radiall	R412.710.124	BX81279
10 dB attenuator	Radiall	R412.710.124	BX81280
Outdoor Antenna Calibration Site	RISE	OATS	2
Biconical antenna	Schwarzbeck	VHBB 9124	1473

Biconical antenna	Schwarzbeck	VHBB 9124	1478
Hybrid antenna	Chase	CBL 6111A	1541
Hybrid antenna	Chase	CBL 6111A	1813

2.10.2.4 Measurement Procedure

The calibrations of absolute gain and antenna factor were performed at the open area test site "Maxwell" (31x26 m) at RISE. The standard that describes the method is the SSM from CISPR 16-1-16 (2014).

The full calibration method requires three site attenuation measurements using three different antennas measured in pairs. The polarization used during measurements is horizontal. The travelling standards were complemented with antennas from RISE to form each three-antenna set. The expressions for the antenna factors can be expressed in terms of the ground wave field strength term and measured site attenuations. The setup is shown in Fig. 2-16:

Fig. 2-16 Setup of the calibration

The three equations associated with the three site attenuation measurements are Eq. (1), (2), and (3).

$$AF_1 + AF_2 = A_1 + K_{SSM}, \tag{1}$$

$$AF_1 + AF_3 = A_2 + K_{SSM} \tag{2}$$

$$AF_1 + AF_3 = A_2 + K_{SSM} \tag{3}$$

where K_{SSM} is calculated according to:

$$K_{SSM} = 20 \log \left(\frac{39.8}{f_{MHz}} \right) - 20 \log [e_0(i, j|H)]. \quad (4)$$

(All equations in dB)

e_0 is calculated according to

$$e_0(i, j|H) = \frac{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{R_{ij}}{r_{ij}}\right)^2 - 2\left(\frac{R_{ij}}{r_{ij}}\right) \cos[2\pi f_{MHz}(r_{ij} - R_{ij})/300]}}{R_{ij}}. \quad (5)$$

R_{ij} is the direct wave and is calculated by:

$$R_{ij} = \sqrt{d^2 + (h_j - h_i)^2}. \quad (6)$$

r_{ij} is the ground-reflected wave and is calculated by:

$$r_{ij} = \sqrt{d^2 + (h_j + h_i)^2}. \quad (7)$$

To reduce antenna impedance mismatch, 10 dB attenuators were applied at the antenna's connectors. Ferrites clamps are applied to the cables at least the first meter both horizontally and vertically on both the transmitting and receiving antenna cables, to serve as common mode chokes. The ferrite clamps were placed no more than 20 cm apart.

For the biconical antennas no correction from Near-Free Space Antenna Factor, NFSAF, to Free-Space Antenna Factor, FSAF, was applied as agreed upon in the pre-requisites.

2.10.2.5 Measurement Results

Tab. 2-12 Measurement results for 10 meter measurement distance and horizontal polarization

Relevant travelling Standard	Frequency	Antenna Factor dB(1/m)	Measurement Uncertainty (dB) (k=2)	Ambient Temperature (°C)	Ambient Humidity (%rh)
Biconical antenna	30	18.51	1.00	24±5	60±10
	60	7.21	1.00	24±5	60±10
	100	11.10	1.00	24±5	60±10
	200	15.33	1.00	24±5	60±10
	300	19.33	1.00	24±5	60±10
Log periodic antenna	200	11.49	1.00	24±5	60±10

	300	13.19	1.00	24±5	60±10
	500	17.43	1.00	24±5	60±10
	800	20.84	1.00	24±5	60±10
	1000	21.83	1.00	24±5	60±10

2.10.2.6 Detailed Uncertainty Budget

Tab. 2-13 Detailed Uncertainty Budget

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of Hz						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (Lin)
VNA accuracy	B	0.023	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.012
VNA temp drift	B	0.006	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.003
Connector repeatability	A	0.002	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.001
Uncertainty in distance	B	0.029	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.015
Pre-amplifier temperature drift	B	0.059	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.030
Frequency uncertainty	B	0.000	Normal	1	1/2	0.000
Uncertainty in K_{SSM}	B	0.000	Normal	1	1	0.000
Mismatch	B	0.009	U-shaped	$\sqrt{2}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.006
Phase center variations	B	0.035	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.018
Site and mast	A	0.053	Normal	1	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.046
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0.122
Total uncertainty (K=2) dB						1.00

2.11 Annex A2

TECHNICAL PROTOCOL

Bilateral Comparison of Open Area Test Site Antenna Measurements between TÜRKİYE TÜBİTAK UME and SWEDEN RISE

Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II

22RPT04 RFMicrowave2

TÜBİTAK UME

(Version 1.1)

June, 2024

Introduction

Biconical and log-periodic antennas are widely utilized in the measurement of electric field component of the electromagnetic waves radiated from broadcasting in TV and radio communications and in electromagnetic compatibility/interference (EMC/EMI) testing in accordance with the commercial and military standards in the frequency range of 30 MHz – 1 GHz. Therefore, the calibration of biconical and log-periodic antennas are of fundamental importance for the traceability of the free space antenna factor measurements. This kind of antennas must be calibrated by National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) or accredited calibration laboratories in accordance with international standards such as CSPR 16-1-6 [1]. It was settled to performing a comparison measurements regarding free space antenna factor measurements, which is one of the work packages within the scope of the EURAMET 22RPT04 RF and Microwave Metrology Capability Development II Project, which started on 01 May 2023. As a result of this, it has been planned to organise a bilateral comparison on open area test site free space antenna calibration between TÜBİTAK UME and RISE.

TÜBİTAK UME is acting as the pilot institute. The travelling standards will be provided by TÜBİTAK UME. TÜBİTAK UME will be responsible to monitoring performance of travelling standards during the circulation and the evaluation and reporting of the comparison results.

The comparison will be carried out in accordance with the CCEM Guidelines for Planning, Organizing, Conducting and Reporting Key, Supplementary and Pilot Comparisons [2].

Travelling Standards

The travelling standards will be supplied by TÜBİTAK UME. The photos and the general specifications of the travelling standards are presented in Figure1 and Table 1, respectively.

(a) Biconical antenna

(b) Log periodic antenna

Figure 1. The photos of the travelling standards (a) Biconical antenna (b) Log periodic antenna.

Table 1. The general specifications of the travelling standards

No	Name	Manufacturer/Model	Serial number	General specifications
1	Biconical antenna	Schaffner / /VBA61006A	1298	Frequency range: 30 MHz – 300 MHz
2	Log periodic antenna	Schwarzbeck / VUSLP 9111B	00509	Frequency range: 200 MHz – 3 GHz

Participant Institutes

The pilot laboratory for this comparison is TÜBİTAK UME. The participating institutes and contact persons with their addresses are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The information of the participant institutes

Country	Institute	Acronym	Shipping Address	Contact Person
Türkiye	TÜBİTAK Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü	TÜBİTAK UME (Pilot laboratory)	TÜBİTAK Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü (UME) TÜBİTAK Gebze Yerleşkesi Barış Mah. Dr. Zeki Acar Cad. No:1 41470 Gebze-Kocaeli, TURKEY	Mehmet Çınar mehmet.cinar@tubitak.gov.tr Tel: +90 262 679 50 00
Sweden	Research Institutes of Sweden	RISE	Research Institutes of SWEDEN (RISE) Mats Cedheim/Hus 15 Brinellgatan 4, 504 62 Borås Sweden	Mats Cedheim mats.cedheim@ri.se Tel: +46 10 516 60 86

Time Schedule

The comparison will be organized in a single loop of two laboratories in order to allow close monitoring of the behaviour of the standard. The time schedule for the comparison measurements is given in Table 3. Any deviation in the agreed plan should be approved by the pilot institute.

Table 3. The time schedule for the comparison measurements

Participant	Country	Measurement Dates
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	8 April 2024 – 28 April 2024
RISE	Sweden	20 May 2024 – 21 June 2024
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	12 August 2024 – 6 September 2024

Transportation of Travelling Standard

The participants will be responsible for arranging transportation to the next participant.

The participants shall inform the pilot laboratory by e-mail when the travelling standards have arrived by filling the following form.

Table 4. Sample form for the information of arrival of the travelling standards

Confirmation Note For Receipt		
Date of Arrival		
NMI		
Name of Responsible Person		
Traveling standard	<input type="checkbox"/> Damaged	<input type="checkbox"/> Not Damaged
Additional Notes:		

The participants shall also inform the next recipient and the pilot institute by e-mail about the shipment of the travelling standards by filling the following form.

Table 5. Sample form for the information of dispatch of the travelling standard

Confirmation Note For Dispatch	
Date of Shipment	
NMI	
Name of Responsible Person	
Shipment Information (company name etc.)	
Additional Notes:	

Failure of Travelling Standards

In case of any damage or malfunction of the travelling standards, the comparison will be carried out after the travelling standard(s) are repaired or supply new standard(s).

Financial Aspects

Each participant institute is responsible for its own costs for the measurements as well as any damage that may occur within its country.

The overall costs for the organization of the comparison are covered by pilot institute. The pilot institute has no insurance for any loss or damage of the travelling standard.

Measurement Points and Conditions

The bilateral comparison will be performed by measuring the biconical and log periodic antennas at 10 meter distance and horizontal polarization. The bilateral comparison frequencies are 30 MHz, 60 MHz, 100 MHz, 200 MHz, 300 MHz for biconical antenna and, 200 MHz, 300 MHz, 500 MHz, 800 MHz and 1000 MHz for log periodic antenna, respectively. The antenna factors must be measured for each frequency. The antenna factor measurements must be performed in accordance with CISPR 16-1-6 [1] standard site method.

The quantities to be measured and the measurement points are given in Table 6.

Table 6. Measurement points & conditions

Relevant travelling Standard	Measurement frequencies (MHz)	Polarization	Measurement distance (Meter)	Height (Meter)
Biconical antenna	30	Horizontal	10	Transmitter Antenna:>2m Receiver Antenna: 1 m-4 m scan
	60			
	100			
	200			
	300			
Log periodic antenna	200			
	300			
	500			
	800			
	1000			

Method of Computation of the Reference Value

The reference value and associated uncertainty for each test point will be a weighted mean and weighted uncertainty, respectively, calculated from the results of two participating laboratories. The antennas shall also be measured by TÜBİTAK UME prior to shipment to RISE and on its immediate return from RISE, and an additional component of uncertainty will be applied for the stability of the instrument transformer derived from the spread of those results.

The Comparison Reference Value (CRV) is calculated separately for each parameter. The CRV is considered as an estimation of the measurand according to the measurements provided by the participating laboratories. This estimation, x_{ref} , is determined as a weighted mean of the provided results where the weights are the inverse values of the squares of the associated standard uncertainties [3].

The weighted mean x_{ref} of the data set and the associated expanded uncertainty $U(x_{ref})$ are obtained from

$$x_{ref} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{x_i}{U^2(x_i)}}{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{U^2(x_i)}} \quad (1)$$

$$U(x_{ref}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{x_i}{U^2(x_i)}}{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{U^2(x_i)}} \quad (2)$$

Calculation of degrees of equivalence

The results of the comparison are reported as the degrees of equivalence (DoE) and the CRV.

The degrees of equivalence of each participant are calculated as:

$$D_i = x_i - x_{ref} \quad (3)$$

Where x_i is the results of the participant and x_{ref} is the CRV.

The expanded uncertainty of the degree of equivalence for a participant's result $U(D_i)$ is calculated as:

$$U^2(D_i) = U^2(x_i) - U^2(x_{ref}) \quad (4)$$

For each participant's result, the normalized error (E_n) is calculated as:

$$E_n = \frac{|D_i|}{U(D_i)} \quad (5)$$

The participant results are regarded as satisfactory if $E_n \leq 1$.

Measurement Instructions

Precautions

Avoid extreme temperature, humidity or pressure changes as well as violent impacts.

Before the Measurements

It should be allowed to stabilize in a temperature and humidity controlled environment for at least 1 day before commencing measurements.

Before the measurements, mechanical controls of the antennas should be done.

Before the measurements, connector controls of the antennas should be done.

Environmental Conditions

The ambient temperature and humidity must be measured. No corrections will be performed for temperature and humidity effects.

Preferably, the references used equipment should be in a temperature controlled room at 22 ± 2 °C. The passive antenna do not vary significant variation in the its performance in the temperature range -5 °C to +35 °C.

Method of Measurement

The antenna factors will be measured 10 m distance and horizontal polarization according to CISPR 16-1-6 (2017) standard site method (SSM) in the open area test site (OATS) [3].

Measurement Uncertainty

The uncertainty of measurement shall be calculated according to the JCGM 100 “Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement” [2] for the coverage probability of approximately 95%.

The detailed measurement uncertainty budget is provided for each of the following frequencies:

30 MHz, 60 MHz, 100 MHz, 200 MHz, 300 MHz for biconical antenna and 200 MHz, 300 MHz, 500 MHz, 800 MHz and 1000 MHz for log periodic antenna.

The example uncertainty budget shown below for the calculation antenna factor may be used by participant laboratories. In the event of other the sources of the uncertainty, the participant laboratories could apply them in the uncertainty table given below page.

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of Hz						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
Transmit antenna mismatch	B					
Receive antenna mismatch	B					
Effect of the site	B					
....	B					
....	B					
....	A					
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						

Reporting of Results

For the measurement results of the participants, the measurement report format given in Annex A will be used and the measurement report containing the measurement results of the participants will be sent to the pilot laboratory by e-mail within three weeks after the completion of the measurements.

Final Report of the Comparison

The pilot laboratory is responsible for the preparation of a comparison report.

The draft version of the comparison report will be issued within two months after receiving the participant report by the pilot institute. Draft report will be sent to the RISE for discussion and approval. This draft will be confidential to the participants.

The participant will have two weeks to send their comments on Draft Report. After approval, Draft Report will become the Final Report. The Final Report will form the basis for the publication of results.

References

- [1] CISPR 16-1-6, "Radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus - EMC Antenna calibration", Edition 1.1, 2017-1
- [2] CCEM Guidelines for Planning, Organizing, Conducting and Reporting Key, Supplementary and Pilot Comparisons, Ver. 2.1, 2017 (available on the BIPM website: https://www.bipm.org/utis/common/pdf/CC/CCEM/ccem_guidelines.pdf).
- [3] Evaluation of measurement data - Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM), JCGM 100, First edition, September 2008 (available on the BIPM website: http://www.bipm.org/utis/common/documents/jcgm/JCGM_100_2008_E.pdf)

2.12 Annex B2

Measurement Report for Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II (22RPT04 RF&Microwave2)

Participant Information

Institute Name	
Contact Person	
Telephone No	
Fax No	
E-mail	
Address	

Measurement Date

Measurement Dates –
--------------------------	---------------

References Used In Measurement

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No

Measurement Procedure

Measurement Results

Table. Measurement results for 10 meter measurement distance and horizontal polarization

Relevant travelling Standard	Frequency	Antenna Factor dB(1/m)	Measurement Uncertainty (dB) (k=2)	Ambient Temperature (°C)	Ambient Humidity (%rh)
Biconical antenna	30				
	60				
	100				
	200				
	300				

Log periodic antenna	200				
	300				
	500				
	800				
	1000				

Detailed Uncertainty Budget

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of Hz						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						

3. SUPPLEMENTARY COMPARISON OF 1 GHZ TO 40 GHZ ANTENNA FACTOR MEASUREMENTS

Partners: TÜBİTAK UME, RISE, CMI

May 2025

3.1 Introduction

A supplementary comparison was organized between TÜBİTAK UME, CMI and RISE for the calibrations of free space antenna factor in the frequency range 1-40 GHz. The comparison was performed within the scope of the Development of RF Microwave Metrology Capability II (22RPT04 RF Microwave 2).

Horn antennas are commonly used in several different environments, for instance various electromagnetic research projects as well as in conducting testing for electromagnetic compatibility/interference (EMC/EMI). The calibration of the antennas can be done according to any of several different standards, for instance CISPR 16-1-6 (2014) [3.7], or methods like the Standard Site Method (SSM), three-antenna method (TAM) or Standard antenna method (SAM). Ultimately, they must be traceable back to an NMI.

The comparison was conducted in accordance with the Technical Protocol of “Supplementary Comparison Between SWEDEN RISE, TÜRKİYE TÜBİTAK UME and CZECH REPUBLIC CMI” and, given in Appendix B3, which was prepared by CMI and approved by TÜBİTAK UME and RISE.

3.2 Organisation of the comparison

3.2.1 Pilot institute

This comparison was piloted by RISE. The travelling standards were provided by TÜBİTAK UME. TÜBİTAK UME was responsible for monitoring the performance of travelling standards during the circulation. RISE and CMI were responsible for the evaluation and reporting of the comparison results.

3.2.2 Participating institutes

The participating institutes are listed in Tab. 3-1.

Tab. 3-1 List of participants

Acronym of Institute	Country	Contact Person	Shipping Address
CMI	Czech Republic	Tomáš Pavlíček tpavlicek@cmi.cz Tel: +420 266 020 185	Český metrologický institut Radiová 1136/3, 102 00 Praha, Czech Republic
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	Mehmet Çınar mehmet.cinar@tubitak.gov.tr Tel: +90 262 679 50 00	TÜBİTAK Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü (UME) TÜBİTAK Gebze Yerleşkesi Barış Mah. Dr. Zeki Acar Cad. No:1 41470 Gebze-Kocaeli, Türkiye
RISE	Sweden	Mats Cedheim mats.cedheim@ri.se Tel: +46 10 516 60 86	Research Institutes of SWEDEN (RISE) Mats Cedheim/Hus 15 Brinellgatan 4, 504 62 Borås Sweden

3.2.3 Comparison schedule

The comparison was organized in a single loop of three laboratories to allow close monitoring of the behaviour of the travelling standards. All the participants had about 22 weeks to carry out the measurements and transportation. A delay, compared to the planned schedule, occurred mainly due to the delay of the other

comparisons at scope of the Development of RF Microwave Metrology Capability II (22RPT04 RF Microwave 2). The actual time schedule is given in Tab. 3-2.

Tab. 3-2 The actual time schedule for the comparison

Institute	Country	Measurement Dates
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	03.05.2024 - 06.05.2024
RISE	Sweden	17.06.2024 – 19.06.2024
CMI	Czech Republic	21.06.2024 – 02.08 2024
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	15.10.2024 - 17.10.2024

3.3 Travelling standards

3.3.1 Description of the Standard

The travelling standards were supplied by TÜBİTAK UME. These standards were chosen for their high accuracy and stability over time. The photos and the general specifications of the travelling standards are presented in Fig. 3-1 and Tab. 3-3, respectively.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3-1 Horn antenna ETSI 3115 1-18 GHz (a), Horn antenna Pasternak 18-26.5 GHz (b), Horn antenna TÜBİTAK UME 26.5-40 GHz (c)

Tab. 3-3 General specifications of the travelling standards

Name	Manufacturer	Model	Serial Number	Frequency Range
Double-ridged horn antenna	ETS-Lindgren	Model 3115	00158093	1 - 18 GHz
Horn antenna	Pasternack	PA9852-20	004	18 - 26.5 GHz
Horn antenna	TÜBİTAK UME	EMC2015-1	005	26.5 – 40 GHz

3.3.2 Measured Quantities and Conditions of the Measurement

The comparison will consist of the measurement of boresight gain of three horn antennas at frequencies specified in this chapter. The boresight line is taken to be normal to the waveguide flange of the antenna and not normal to the aperture of the antenna. The supplementary comparison will be performed by measuring the antennas in free space condition at a fixed distance of 3 m. The measured quantity is the antenna factor. For horn antenna No. 1, the supplementary comparison frequencies are 1 GHz, 1.5 GHz, 2 GHz, 2.5 GHz, 3.5 GHz, 4 GHz, 5 GHz, 6 GHz, 7.5 GHz, 8 GHz, 10 GHz, 12 GHz, 14 GHz, 16 GHz and 18 GHz. For horn antenna No. 2, the frequencies are 18 GHz, 20 GHz, 22.5 GHz, 25 GHz and 26.5 GHz. And for horn antenna No. 3, the frequencies are 26.5 GHz, 29 GHz, 32 GHz, 36 GHz and 40 GHz.

The antenna factors shall be measured for each frequency listed in Tab. 3-4.

Tab. 3-4 Measurement points & conditions

Relevant travelling Standard	Measurement frequency (GHz)	Condition
No 1. Model 3115	1	Distance 3 m AF_{3M}
	1.5	
	2	
	2.5	
	3.5	
	4	
	5	
	6	
	7.5	
	8	
	10	
	12	
	14	
	16	
18		

No 2. PA9852-20	18	Distance 3m (Far-field antenna factor AF)
	20	
	22.5	
	25	
	26.5	
No 3. EMC2015-1	26.5	
	29	
	32	
	36	
	40	

3.4 Methods of Measurement

The measurements were performed according to each participants' measurement procedure. The detailed measurement methods used by the participants were given in the comparison reports of the participants in Annex A.3.

3.5 Results of the Participating Institutes

The measurement results of the participating institutes (x_i) and their standard uncertainties ($u(x_i)$) are presented for each frequency in Tab. 3-5. TÜBİTAK UME measurements specified in Tab. 3-5 are the average of the measurements taken before the comparison and after the RISE measurements.

Tab. 3-5 Results of the participating institutes

Relevant Travelling Standard	Frequency (GHz)	Participating Institute	Antenna Factor dB (1/m)	Standard Uncertainty (k=2) (dB)
ETS Lindgren 3115	1	RISE	24.10	0.84
		CMI	23.33	0.35
		TÜBİTAK UME	23.40	0.58
	1.5	RISE	25.64	0.84
		CMI	25.76	0.25
		TÜBİTAK UME	25.40	0.58
	2	RISE	28.64	0.84
		CMI	28.75	0.32
		TÜBİTAK UME	28.40	0.58

	2.5	RISE	27.88	0.84
		CMI	27.92	0.25
		TÜBİTAK UME	27.70	0.58
	3.5	RISE	30.76	0.84
		CMI	30.65	0.25
		TÜBİTAK UME	30.50	0.58
	4	RISE	31.77	0.84
		CMI	31.96	0.25
		TÜBİTAK UME	31.70	0.58
	5	RISE	32.30	0.88
		CMI	33.00	0.31
		TÜBİTAK UME	32.70	0.58
	6	RISE	34.90	0.88
		CMI	35.49	0.35
		TÜBİTAK UME	35.50	0.58
	7.5	RISE	37.14	0.88
		CMI	37.71	0.54
		TÜBİTAK UME	37.40	0.58
	8	RISE	36.92	0.88
		CMI	37.07	0.43
		TÜBİTAK UME	36.80	0.58
10	RISE	38.26	0.88	
	CMI	38.28	0.48	
	TÜBİTAK UME	38.40	0.58	
12	RISE	38.97	0.88	

		CMI	38.72	0.38
		TÜBİTAK UME	38.70	0.58
		RISE	40.80	0.88
	14	CMI	41.22	0.34
		TÜBİTAK UME	41.20	0.58
		RISE	38.12	0.88
	16	CMI	38.19	0.59
		TÜBİTAK UME	38.70	0.58
		RISE	43.10	0.88
	18	CMI	42.27	0.41
		TÜBİTAK UME	42.30	0.58
		RISE	36.98	0.88
Pasternak PA9852-20	18	CMI	37.16	0.29
		TÜBİTAK UME	37.00	0.47
		RISE	36.85	0.88
	20	CMI	37.12	0.31
		TÜBİTAK UME	37.00	0.47
		RISE	37.30	0.96
	22.5	CMI	37.55	0.30
		TÜBİTAK UME	37.30	0.47
		RISE	37.40	0.96
	25	CMI	37.81	0.31
		TÜBİTAK UME	37.50	0.47
		RISE	37.56	0.96
	26.5	CMI	37.95	0.30
		RISE		

		TÜBİTAK UME	37.90	0.47
EMC2015-1	26.5	RISE	39.13	0.96
		CMI	39.54	0.35
		TÜBİTAK UME	39.60	0.52
	29	RISE	39.54	0.96
		CMI	39.79	0.34
		TÜBİTAK UME	39.60	0.52
	32	RISE	40.12	0.96
		CMI	40.27	0.35
		TÜBİTAK UME	40.10	0.52
	36	RISE	40.40	0.96
		CMI	40.76	0.36
		TÜBİTAK UME	40.40	0.52
	40	RISE	42.06	0.96
		CMI	41.11	0.41
		TÜBİTAK UME	40.80	0.52

3.6 Calculation of Comparison Reference Values and associated uncertainties

The Comparison Reference Value (CRV) is calculated separately for each parameter. The CRV is considered as an estimation of the measurand according to the measurements provided by the participating laboratories. This estimation, x_{ref} , is determined as a weighted mean of the provided results where the weights are the inverse values of the squares of the associated standard uncertainties [3.2].

The weighted mean x_{ref} of the data set and the associated expanded uncertainty $U(x_{ref})$ are obtained from

$$x_{ref} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{U^2(x_i)}} \quad (3.1)$$

$$U^2(x_{ref}) = 1 / \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{U^2(x_i)} \quad (3.2)$$

Tab. 3-6 Comparison reference values and expanded uncertainties for all measurements

Relevant Travelling Standard	Frequency (GHz)	X_{ref} (dB)	$U(X_{ref})$ (dB)
ETS Lindgren 3115	1	23.435	0.144
	1.5	25.701	0.113
	2	28.668	0.136
	2.5	27.886	0.113
	3.5	30.636	0.113
	4	31.910	0.113
	5	32.882	0.133
	6	35.434	0.145
	7.5	37.498	0.185
	8	36.968	0.165
	10	38.319	0.175
	12	38.743	0.153
	14	41.175	0.142
	16	38.395	0.193
	18	42.386	0.160
Pasternak PA9852-20	18	37.107	0.121
	20	37.066	0.126
	22.5	37.468	0.125
	25	37.697	0.127
	26.5	37.913	0.125
EMC2015-1	26.5	39.525	0.142
	29	39.719	0.139

	32	40.210	0.142
	36	40.625	0.145
	40	41.104	0.156

3.7 Calculation of degrees of equivalence

The results of the comparison are reported as the degrees of equivalence (DoE) and the CRV.

The degrees of equivalence of each participant are calculated as:

$$D_i = x_i - x_{ref}, \quad (3.3)$$

where x_i is the results of the participant and x_{ref} is the CRV.

The expanded uncertainty of the degree of equivalence for a participant's result $U(D_i)$ is calculated as:

$$U^2(D_i) = U^2(x_i) - U^2(x_{ref}). \quad (3.4)$$

For each participant's result, the normalized error (E_n) is calculated as:

$$E_n = \frac{|D_i|}{U(D_i)}. \quad (3.5)$$

The participant results are regarded as satisfactory if $E_n \leq 1$.

Tab. 3-7 The degrees of equivalence (D_i), its uncertainties ($U(D_i)$) and E_n values

Relevant Travelling Standard	Frequency (GHz)	Participating Institute	D_i (dB)	$U(D_i)$ (dB)	E_n
ETS Lindgren 3115	1	RISE	0.665	0.831	0.80
		CMI	-0.105	0.209	0.50
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.035	0.524	0.07
	1.5	RISE	-0.061	0.852	0.07
		CMI	0.059	0.116	0.51
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.301	0.555	0.54
	2	RISE	-0.028	0.837	0.03
		CMI	0.082	0.180	0.46

		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.268	0.533	0.50
2.5		RISE	0.006	0.852	0.01
		CMI	0.034	0.116	0.29
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.186	0.555	0.34
3.5		RISE	0.124	0.852	0.15
		CMI	0.014	0.116	0.12
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.136	0.555	0.25
4		RISE	-0.140	0.852	0.16
		CMI	0.050	0.116	0.43
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.210	0.555	0.38
5		RISE	-0.582	0.885	0.66
		CMI	0.118	0.168	0.70
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.182	0.535	0.34
6		RISE	-0.534	0.877	0.61
		CMI	0.056	0.207	0.27
		TÜBİTAK UME	0.066	0.523	0.13
7.5		RISE	-0.358	0.845	0.42
		CMI	0.212	0.413	0.51
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.098	0.468	0.21
8		RISE	-0.048	0.863	0.06
		CMI	0.102	0.290	0.35
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.168	0.498	0.34
10		RISE	-0.059	0.854	0.07
		CMI	-0.039	0.345	0.11
		TÜBİTAK UME	0.081	0.484	0.17

	12	RISE	0.227	0.872	0.26
		CMI	-0.023	0.238	0.10
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.043	0.513	0.08
	14	RISE	-0.375	0.879	0.43
		CMI	0.045	0.197	0.23
		TÜBİTAK UME	0.025	0.526	0.05
	16	RISE	-0.275	0.838	0.33
		CMI	-0.205	0.470	0.44
		TÜBİTAK UME	0.305	0.456	0.67
	18	RISE	0.714	0.866	0.82
		CMI	-0.116	0.269	0.43
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.086	0.504	0.17
Pasternak PA9852-20	18	RISE	-0.127	0.893	0.14
		CMI	0.053	0.168	0.32
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.107	0.416	0.26
	20	RISE	-0.216	0.889	0.24
		CMI	0.054	0.187	0.29
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.066	0.410	0.16
	22.5	RISE	-0.168	0.983	0.17
		CMI	0.082	0.175	0.47
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.168	0.412	0.41
	25	RISE	-0.297	0.981	0.30
		CMI	0.113	0.185	0.61
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.197	0.409	0.48
	26.5	RISE	-0.353	0.983	0.36

		CMI	0.037	0.175	0.21
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.013	0.412	0.03
EMC2015-1	26.5	RISE	-0.395	0.973	0.41
		CMI	0.015	0.215	0.07
		TÜBİTAK UME	0.075	0.452	0.17
	29	RISE	-0.179	0.974	0.18
		CMI	0.071	0.205	0.35
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.119	0.456	0.26
	32	RISE	-0.090	0.973	0.09
		CMI	0.060	0.215	0.28
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.110	0.452	0.24
	36	RISE	-0.225	0.971	0.23
		CMI	0.135	0.225	0.60
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.225	0.449	0.50
	40	RISE	0.956	0.963	0.99
		CMI	0.006	0.278	0.02
		TÜBİTAK UME	-0.304	0.433	0.70

Figures of the degrees of equivalence (D_i) and its uncertainties ($U(D_i)$) are given in Figures 2-26.

Fig. 3-2 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 1 GHz

Fig. 3-3 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 1.5 GHz

Fig. 3-4 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 2 GHz

Fig. 3-5 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 2.5 GHz

Fig. 3-6 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 3.5 GHz

Fig. 3-7 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 4 GHz

Fig. 3-8 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 5 GHz

Fig. 3-9 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 6 GHz

Fig. 3-10 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 7.5 GHz

Fig. 3-11 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 8 GHz

Fig. 3-12 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 10 GHz

Fig. 3-13 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 12 GHz

Fig. 3-14 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 14 GHz

Fig. 3-15 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 16 GHz

Fig. 3-16 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna 3115 @ 18 GHz

Fig. 3-17 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna PA9852-20 @ 18 GHz

Fig. 3-18 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna PA9852-20 @ 20 GHz

Fig. 3-19 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna PA9852-20 @ 22.5 GHz

Fig. 3-20 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna PA9852-20 @ 25 GHz

Fig. 3-21 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna PA9852-20 @ 26.5 GHz

Fig. 3-22 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna EMC2015-1@ 26.5 GHz

Fig. 3-23 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna EMC2015-1@ 29 GHz

Fig. 3-24 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna EMC2015-1@ 32 GHz

Fig. 3-25 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna EMC2015-1@ 36 GHz

Fig. 3-26 Degrees of equivalence for horn antenna EMC2015-1@ 40 GHz

3.8 Conclusion

The comparison has been conducted between TÜBİTAK UME, CMI and RISE. As traveling standard, three horn antennas were used. They have low dependence on ambient parameters and a very stable behavior. The travelling standards were circulated without major problem from May 2024 to September 2024.

The CRV was determined by using the weighted mean of the participants measurement results. In the CRV calculations, the values used in the comparison report were obtained by converting the decibel values to linear values.

The comparison results showed a good agreement between TÜBİTAK UME, CMI and RISE for the three horn antennas ETSI 3115 (1 GHz - 18 GHz), Pasternak PA9852-20 818 GHz-26.5 GHz) and TÜBİTAK UME EMC2015-1 (26.5 GHz - 40 GHz) within the stated uncertainties. E_n values for each participant for all measurement points satisfy Equation (3.5). The results of this comparison will lead participants to improve their calibration setups and revise their uncertainty budgets.

3.9 References

- [3.1] J. Randa: "Update to proposal for KCRV & degree of equivalence for GTRF key comparisons", NIST, February 2005.
- [3.2] W. Bich, M. Cox, T. Estler, L. Nielsen, W. Woeger, "Proposed guidelines for the evaluation of key comparison data", April 2002.
- [3.3] Cox M. G.: The Evaluation of Key Comparison Data. Metrology 39, pp. 589-595, 2002.
- [3.4] JCGM 100:2008 Evaluation of measurement data. – Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement. BULMAM GEREK
- [3.5] EA-4/02M:2022 Evaluation of the Uncertainty of Measurement in calibration.
- [3.6] Final Report EURAMET.EM-S43 (EURAMET Project no: 1492), September 2022.
- [7] CISPR 16-1-6, "Radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus - EMC Antenna calibration", Edition 1.1, 2017-1

3.10 Measurement reports for each participant

3.10.1 TÜBİTAK UME

3.10.1.1 Participant Information

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3.10.1.2 Measurement date

Measurement Dates	15.10.2024 – 17.10.2024
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3.10.1.3 References Used In Measurement

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No
Network Analyzer	Anritsu	MS4644B	1905926
10 dB Coaxial Fixed Attenuator	Keysight	8491B	MY39271760
10 dB Coaxial Fixed Attenuator	Keysight	8491B	MY39271778
6 dB Coaxial Fixed Attenuator	Agilent	2,92 mm (K) RF connector	50603
6 dB Coaxial Fixed Attenuator	Agilent	2,92 mm (K) RF connector	50407
Horn Antenna	Schaffner	BHA9118	9014
Horn Antenna	ARA	DRG118/A	1175

Horn Antenna	Pasternack	PE9852-20	002
Horn Antenna	TÜBITAK UME	MEH002	006
Horn Antenna	Pasternack	PE9850-20	001
Horn Antenna	TÜBITAK UME	MEH001	007

3.10.1.4 Measurement Procedure

The antenna measurements were performed vertical polarization in accordance standard site method (SSM) [1], [2] in semi-anechoic chamber. Its dimensions are 18 meters length x 13 meters width x 9 meters height. Before the measurements, the floor of the semi-anechoic chamber was covered with absorbers. Also, three antennas are required for SSM (Fig. 3-27). For this reason, apart from the travel standards, the second and third similar horn antennas were provided by TUBITAK UME. The heights of the transmitter and receiver antennas were adjusted to approximately 3 meters at height from the floor thanks to the rail system. Then, the distance between the apertures of the transmitting and receiving antennas was adjusted to 3 meters.

The measurements were carried out using 50 Ω low-loss RF cables. Also, 10 dB attenuators were used on the antenna connectors for 1-18 GHz horn antenna measurements and 6 dB attenuators were used on the antenna connectors for 18-26.5 and 26.5-40 GHz horn antenna measurements.

After the measurement setup was prepared, measurements were performed using the network analyzer (Fig. 3-28).

Fig. 3-27 Three site attenuation measurements using three different horn antennas in pairs

Fig. 3-28 Measurement set-up for SSM at fully anechoic chamber

3.10.1.5 References

- [1] ANSI C63.5 (2017), American National Standard for Electromagnetic Compatibility – Radiated Emission Measurements in Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) Control – Calibration of Antennas (9 kHz to 40 GHz).
- [2] CISPR 16-1-6, Edition 1.1 (2017), Specification for radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus and methods - Part 1-6: Radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus - EMC antenna calibration.

3.10.1.6 Measurement Results

Measurement results were given in Tab. 3-8.

Tab. 3-8 Measurement results

Relevant Travelling Standard	Measurement Frequency (GHz)	Antenna Factor (dB(1/m))	Measurement Uncertainty (dB), (k =2)	Ambient Temperature (°C)	Ambient Humidity (%rh)
No 1. Model 3115	1.0	23.4	0.58	22 ± 2	45 ± 10
	1.5	25.4			
	2.0	28.4			
	2.5	27.7			
	3.5	30.5			
	4.0	31.7			
	5.0	32.7			
	6.0	35.5			
	7.5	37.4			
	8.0	36.8			
	10.0	38.4			
	12.0	38.7			
	14.0	41.2			

	16.0	38.7		
	18.0	42.3		
No 2. PA9852-20	18.0	37.0	0.47	
	20.0	37.0		
	22.5	37.3		
	25.0	37.5		
	26.5	37.9		
No 3. EMC2015-1	26.5	39.6	0.52	
	29.0	39.6		
	32.0	40.1		
	36.0	40.4		
	40.0	40.8		

3.10.1.7 Detailed Uncertainty Budgets

Tab. 3-9 No 1 Model 3115

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 1 GHz to 18 GHz for No 1 Model 3115 measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (dB)
Receiver reading accuracy after direct connection of cables	B	0.110	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.055
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna1-2	B	0.130	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.065
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna1-3	B	0.130	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.065
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna2-3	B	0.130	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.065
Generator- receiver (direct connection mismatch with an adapter)	B	0.010	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0.866	0.006
Generator-antenna mismatch	B	0.180	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0.866	0.110
Antenna-receiver mismatch	B	0.165	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0.866	0.101
Antenna height positioning	B	0.160	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.080
Antenna distance positioning	B	0.182	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.091
Antenna misalignment	B	0.096	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.048

Effect of phase centre	B	0.270	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.135
Repeatability	A	0.098	Normal	1	1	0.098
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0.58

Tab. 3-10 No 2 PA9852-20

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 18 GHz to 26,5 GHz for No 2 PA9852-20 measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (dB)
Receiver reading accuracy after direct connection of cables	B	0.130	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.065
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna1-2	B	0.150	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.075
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna1-3	B	0.150	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.075
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna2-3	B	0.150	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.075
Generator- receiver (direct connection mismatch with an adapter)	B	0.007	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0.866	0.004
Generator-antenna mismatch	B	0.176	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0.866	0.108
Antenna-receiver mismatch	B	0.140	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0.866	0.086
Antenna height positioning	B	0.122	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.061
Antenna distance positioning	B	0.181	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.090
Antenna misalignment	B	0.047	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0.866	0.023
Repeatability	A	0.040	Normal	1	1	0.040
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0.47

Tab. 3-11 No 3 EMC2015-1

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 26,5 GHz to 40 GHz for No 3 EMC2015-1 measurements						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard uncertainty contribution (dB)
Receiver reading accuracy after direct connection of cables	B	0,130	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,065
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna1-2	B	0,150	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,075
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna1-3	B	0,150	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,075
Receiver reading accuracy after connecting cables to antennas for antenna2-3	B	0,150	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,075
Generator- receiver (direct connection mismatch with an adapter)	B	0,013	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0,866	0,008
Generator-antenna mismatch	B	0,160	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0,866	0,098
Antenna-receiver mismatch	B	0,135	U-distribution	$\sqrt{2}$	0,866	0,083
Antenna height positioning	B	0,076	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,038
Antenna distance positioning	B	0,233	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,116
Antenna misalignment	B	0,090	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	0,866	0,045
Repeatability	A	0,110	Normal	1	1	0,110
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0.52

3.10.2 RISE

3.10.2.1 Participant Information

Institute Name	RISE
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3.10.2.2 Measurement Date

Measurement Dates	01.06.2024.... – 02.06.2024
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3.10.2.3 References Used in Measurement

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No
Network Analyzer	Rohde&Schwarz	ZNB-40	101544
Pre-amplifier (1-18 GHz)	Miteq	AFS44-00102650	646469
Pre-amplifier (18-40 GHz)	Miteq	JS4-18004000-30-5A	642842
Attenuator	Inmet	40AH-10	RISE inv.nr: 900116
Attenuator	Inmet	40AH-10	RISE inv.nr: 900118
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	06240	55
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	08240	119
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	10240	96
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	12240	148478
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	14240	146
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	16240	579
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	18240	477
Standard Gain Horn	Flann	20240	275170

Standard Gain Horn	Flann	22240	274184
Horn Antenna	Rohde&Schwarz	HF 907	102446
Horn Antenna	EMCO	3116	00033927

3.10.2.4 Measurement Procedure

All the antenna calibrations were performed in the fully anechoic chamber “Hertz” at RISE. Two different methods were used for the different frequency ranges.

1-18 GHz: Gain-Transfer (Standard Antenna Method)

The standard antenna method is one in which the unknown gain of a test antenna is measured by comparing it to an antenna with known gain. Ideally the test antenna is illuminated by a plane wave which is polarization matched to it, and the received power is measured into a matched load. The test antenna is then replaced by a gain standard, leaving all other conditions the same. The received power into its matched load is again measured. Now the gain of the test antenna can be calculated from the known gain of the standard antenna and the difference in received power at both measurements.

The gain of the test antenna can be calculated as:

$$(G_T)_{dB} = (G_{ref})_{dB} + 10 \log \left(\frac{P_T}{P_{ref}} \right), \quad (3.6)$$

where:

$(G_T)_{dB}$ = Gain test antenna

$(G_{ref})_{dB}$ = Reference antenna gain

P_T = Received power when using test antenna

P_{ref} = Received power when using reference antenna

The antenna factor of the test antenna can be determined as:

$$AF_{dB/m} = 20 \log(f_{MHz}) - (G_T)_{dB} - 29.79, \quad (3.6)$$

where

$AF_{dB/m}$ = Antenna factor in dB

f_{MHz} = Frequency in MHz

18-40 GHz: Three-antenna method

The 3-antenna method requires three site attenuation measurements under identical geometries (h_{TX} , h_{RX} , R) using three different antennas taken in pairs. The heights are to be the same for both sides, that is $h_{TX}=h_{RX}=1.5m$. The three equations associated with the three site attenuation measurements are Eq. (3.7), (3.8),

and (3.9).

$$AF_1 + AF_2 = A_1 + 20 \log f_M - 48.92 + E_D^{max}, \quad (3.7)$$

$$AF_1 + AF_2 = A_1 + 20 \log f_M - 48.92 + E_D^{max}, \quad (3.8)$$

$$AF_2 + AF_3 = A_3 + 20 \log f_M - 48.92 + E_D^{max}, \quad (3.9)$$

(All equations in dB)

Where:

- E_D^{max} is the maximum received field in dB μ V/m at the separation distance R from the transmitting antenna, calculated according to

$$E_D^{max} = 16.9 - 20 \log (R) \quad (3.10)$$

- AF_1, AF_2, AF_3 are the antenna factors of antennas 1, 2, and 3 in dB (1/m).
- A_1, A_2, A_3 are the measured site attenuation in dB.
- f_M is the frequency in MHz.

3.10.2.5 Measurement results

Relevant travelling Standard	Measurement frequency (GHz)	Antenna Factor (dB(1/m))	Measurement Uncertainty (dB), (k =2)	Ambient Temperature (°C)	Ambient Humidity (%rh)
No 1. Model 3115	1	24.10	0.84	23±5	44±10
	1.5	25.64	0.84	23±5	44±10
	2	28.64	0.84	23±5	44±10
	2.5	27.88	0.84	23±5	44±10
	3.5	30.76	0.84	23±5	44±10
	4	31.77	0.84	23±5	44±10
	5	32.30	0.88	23±5	44±10
	6	34.90	0.88	23±5	44±10
	7.5	37.14	0.88	23±5	44±10
	8	36.92	0.88	23±5	44±10
	10	38.26	0.88	23±5	44±10
	12	38.97	0.88	23±5	44±10
	14	40.80	0.88	23±5	44±10
	16	38.12	0.88	23±5	44±10
No 2. PA9852-20	18	43.10	0.88	23±5	44±10
	18	36.98	0.88	23±5	44±10
	20	36.85	0.88	23±5	44±10
	22.5	37.30	0.96	23±5	44±10
	25	37.40	0.96	23±5	44±10
	26.5	37.56	0.96	23±5	44±10

No 3. EMC2015-1	26.5	39.13	0.96	23±5	44±10
	29	39.54	0.96	23±5	44±10
	32	40.12	0.96	23±5	44±10
	36	40.40	0.96	23±5	44±10
	40	42.06	0.96	23±5	44±10

3.10.2.6 Detailed Uncertainty Budget

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 1-4.5 GHz						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (Lin)
Gain of the reference antenna	B	0.059	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.034
VNA accuracy in P_T	B	0.023	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.013
VNA accuracy in P_{ref}	B	0.023	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	-1	0.013
VNA temperature drift	B	0.023	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.003
Connector repeatability	A	0.002	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.001
Uncertainty in distance	B	0.015	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	2	0.017
Pre-amplifier temperature drift	B	0.042	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.024
Mismatch	B	0.009	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.007
Site and orientation	B	0.012	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.007
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0.101
Total Uncertainty dB (k=2)						0.84

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 4.5-18 GHz						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (Lin)
Gain of the reference antenna	B	0.059	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.034
VNA accuracy in P_T	B	0.023	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.013
VNA accuracy in P_{ref}	B	0.023	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	-1	0.013
VNA temperature drift	B	0.023	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.013
Connector repeatability	A	0.015	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.009
Uncertainty in distance	B	0.015	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	2	0.017
Pre-amplifier temperature drift	B	0.042	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.024
Mismatch	B	0.009	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.007
Site and orientation	B	0.012	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	1	0.007
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0.106
Total Uncertainty dB (k=2)						0.88

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 18-20 GHz						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (Lin)
VNA accuracy	B	0.023	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.012
VNA temp drift	B	0.029	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.015
Uncertainty in distance	B	0.030	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.015
Pre-amplifier temperature drift	B	0.023	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.012
Antenna alignment	B	0.047	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.024
Calculation of E^D_{Max}	B	0.000	Normal	1	1/2	0.000
Connector repeatability	A	0.010	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.005
Mismatch	B	0.009	U-shaped	$\sqrt{2}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.006
Phase centre variations	B	0.035	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.018
Site and mast	B	0.040	Normal	2	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.035
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0.106
Total Uncertainty dB (k=2)						0.88

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of 20-40 GHz						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (Lin)
VNA accuracy	B	0.023	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.012
VNA temp drift	B	0.047	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.024
Uncertainty in distance	B	0.030	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.015
Pre-amplifier temperature drift	B	0.023	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.012
Antenna alignment	B	0.047	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.024
Calculation of E_{Max}^D	B	0.000	Normal	1	1/2	0.000
Connector repeatability	A	0.030	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.015
Mismatch	B	0.009	U-shaped	$\sqrt{2}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.006
Phase centre variations	B	0.035	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.018
Site and mast	B	0.040	Normal	2	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.035
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0.116
Total Uncertainty dB (k=2)						0.96

3.10.3 CMI

3.10.3.1 Participant Information

Institute Name	Czech Metrology Institute (1013 Department of Primary Metrology of RF Electrical Quantities)
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3.10.3.2 Measurement Date

Measurement Dates	July 10 th – 19 th , 2024
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3.10.3.3 Environmental Conditions

Temperature (°C)	23.0 ± 2.0
Relative Humidity (%rh)	70 ± 15

3.10.3.4 Traveling Standards Specification

No.	Name	Manufacturer/Model	Serial number	Frequency range
1	Double-ridged waveguide horn antenna	ETS-Lindgren Model 3115	158093	1 GHz – 18 GHz
2	Horn antenna	Pasternack / PA9852-20	004	18 GHz – 26.5 GHz
3	Horn antenna	TÜBITAK UME / EMC2015-1	005	26.5 GHz – 40 GHz

3.10.3.5 References Used in Measurement

The measurements are metrologically traceable to national/international standards.

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No
Waveguide to coax. transition	Tesla	R14, QBV 1655 20	001
Waveguide to coax. transition	Tesla	R14, QBV 1655 20	001
Waveguide to coax. transition	Tesla	R22, QBV 1095 20	0001
Waveguide to coax. transition	Tesla	R22, QBV 1095 21	0001
Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R48, MC90VO22103E	001
Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R48, MC90VO22103E	002
Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R100, R100-A1	001
Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R100, R100-A2	002
Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R140, R140-A1	001
Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R140, R140-A2	002
Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R220, MC42T61103-18	001

Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R220, MC42T61103-18	002
Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R320, MC28TA611110-B	001
Horn antenna	Milan Chyba Eng.	R320, MC28TA611110-B	002
Power splitter	Hewlett-Packard	11667A	19396
Directional coupler	Milan Chyba Eng.	R220, MC42SO35020	001
Directional coupler	ČVUT – Praha	R320	054
Power meter	Rohde & Schwarz	NRVD	835843/022
Power meter	Rohde & Schwarz	NRVD	100945
Power meter	Agilent	N1911A	MY45100570
Power meter	Hewlett-Packard	E4419A	US38260913
Power sensor	Rohde & Schwarz	NRV-Z55	100290
Power sensor	Rohde & Schwarz	NRV-Z51	836942/010
Power sensor	Rohde & Schwarz	NRV-Z4	848264/008
Power sensor	Rohde & Schwarz	NRV-Z1	839913/009
Power sensor	Hewlett-Packard	R8486A	3318A03345
Power sensor	Hewlett-Packard	8487D	MY50410001
RF synthesizer	Hewlett-Packard	83630B	3722A00516
RF synthesizer	Agilent	E8257D	US46461139
Vector network analyzer	Keysight	E5080A	MY55402057
Vector network analyzer	Agilent	E8364B	MY43040291
Mechanical calibration kit	Hewlett-Packard	85054D	3101A00569
Mechanical calibration kit	Agilent	85056A	3101A02327

3.10.3.6 Measurement Procedure

The calibration of the boresight antenna factor was performed using the three-antenna method in a fully anechoic chamber. The distance between the apertures of the antennas was 3 m.

Fig. 3-29 Simplified measurement configuration of antenna pair

The insertion loss between a given pair of antennas was measured using RF power sensors in a $50\ \Omega$ measuring system. The measurements were made in the reference plane of the coaxial connectors of the traveling standard antennas. The other antennas forming a pair with the antenna under test always satisfied the far-field condition for the given distance of 3 m (under free-space conditions). The antenna factor was calculated from the measured apparent gain.

3.10.3.7 Measurement Results

Travelling standard	Frequency (GHz)	G _{3M} (dB)	AF _{3M} (dB(1/m))	U _c (k = 2) (dB)
No 1. Model 3115, s/n: 00158093	1	6.90	23.33	0.35
	1.5	7.98	25.76	0.25
	2	7.50	28.75	0.32
	2.5	10.26	27.92	0.25
	3.5	10.45	30.65	0.25
	4	10.30	31.96	0.25
	5	11.20	33.00	0.31
	6	10.30	35.49	0.35
	7.5	10.02	37.71	0.54
	8	11.22	37.07	0.43
	10	11.95	38.28	0.48
	12	13.09	38.72	0.38
	14	11.93	41.22	0.34
	16	16.12	38.19	0.59
18	13.06	42.27	0.41	

Travelling standard	Frequency (GHz)	G (dB)	AF (dB(1/m))	U _c (k = 2) (dB)
No 2. PA9852-20, s/n: 004	18	18.17	37.16	0.29
	20	19.12	37.12	0.31
	22.5	19.72	37.55	0.30
	25	20.37	37.81	0.31
	26.5	20.73	37.95	0.30

Travelling standard	Frequency (GHz)	G (dB)	AF (dB(1/m))	U _c (k = 2) (dB)
No 3. EMC2015-1, s/n: 005	26.5	19.15	39.54	0.35
	29	19.68	39.79	0.34
	32	20.06	40.27	0.35
	36	20.59	40.76	0.36
	40	21.15	41.11	0.41

3.10.3.8 Detailed Uncertainty Budget

Travelling standard No 1. Model 3115, s/n: 00158093

f = 1000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.038	normal	1	1	0.038
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.064	U-shape	1.41	1	0.045
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.048	U-shape	1.41	1	0.034
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.131	normal	1	1	0.131
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.014	normal	1	1	0.014
Total (k = 2)						0.35

f = 1500 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.015	normal	1	1	0.015
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.022	U-shape	1.41	1	0.015
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.059	U-shape	1.41	1	0.042
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.067	normal	1	1	0.067
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.018	normal	1	1	0.018
Total (k = 2)						0.25

f = 2000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.035	normal	1	1	0.035
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.038	U-shape	1.41	1	0.027
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.087	U-shape	1.41	1	0.062
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.106	normal	1	1	0.106
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.021	normal	1	1	0.021
Total (k = 2)						0.32

f = 2500 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.016	normal	1	1	0.016
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.016	U-shape	1.41	1	0.012
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.056	U-shape	1.41	1	0.040
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.068	normal	1	1	0.068
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.024	normal	1	1	0.024
Total (k = 2)						0.25

f = 3500 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.006	normal	1	1	0.006
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.038	U-shape	1.41	1	0.027
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.068	U-shape	1.41	1	0.048
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.060	normal	1	1	0.060
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.029	normal	1	1	0.029
Total (k = 2)						0.25

f = 4000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.017	U-shape	1.41	1	0.012
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.072	U-shape	1.41	1	0.051
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.060	normal	1	1	0.060
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.031	normal	1	1	0.031
Total (k = 2)						0.25

f = 5000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.006	normal	1	1	0.006
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.025	U-shape	1.41	1	0.017
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.024	U-shape	1.41	1	0.017
Distance between antennas	B	0.198	rectangular	1.73	1	0.114
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.034	normal	1	1	0.034
Total (k = 2)						0.31

f = 6000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.018	U-shape	1.41	1	0.013
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.058	U-shape	1.41	1	0.041
Distance between antennas	B	0.198	rectangular	1.73	1	0.114
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.060	normal	1	1	0.060
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.036	normal	1	1	0.036
Near-field effects	B	0.067	normal	1	1	0.067
Total (k = 2)						0.35

f = 7500 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.005	normal	1	1	0.005
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.082	U-shape	1.41	1	0.058
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.249	U-shape	1.41	1	0.176
Distance between antennas	B	0.173	rectangular	1.73	1	0.100
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.028	normal	1	1	0.028
Near-field effects	B	0.137	normal	1	1	0.137
Total (k = 2)						0.54

f = 8000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.005	normal	1	1	0.005
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.043	U-shape	1.41	1	0.030
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.116	U-shape	1.41	1	0.082
Distance between antennas	B	0.173	rectangular	1.73	1	0.100
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.024	normal	1	1	0.024
Near-field effects	B	0.137	normal	1	1	0.137
Total (k = 2)						0.43

f = 10000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.005	normal	1	1	0.005
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.046	U-shape	1.41	1	0.033
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.182	U-shape	1.41	1	0.129
Distance between antennas	B	0.173	rectangular	1.73	1	0.100
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.055	normal	1	1	0.055
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Near-field effects	B	0.137	normal	1	1	0.137
Total (k = 2)						0.48

f = 12000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.006	normal	1	1	0.006
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.052	normal	1	1	0.052
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.062	U-shape	1.41	1	0.044
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.097	U-shape	1.41	1	0.068
Distance between antennas	B	0.124	rectangular	1.73	1	0.072
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.048	normal	1	1	0.048
Near-field effects	B	0.111	normal	1	1	0.111
Total (k = 2)						0.38

f = 14000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.057	normal	1	1	0.057
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.026	U-shape	1.41	1	0.018
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.045	U-shape	1.41	1	0.032
Distance between antennas	B	0.124	rectangular	1.73	1	0.072
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.026	normal	1	1	0.026
Near-field effects	B	0.111	normal	1	1	0.111
Total (k = 2)						0.34

f = 16000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.005	normal	1	1	0.005
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.054	normal	1	1	0.054
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.029	U-shape	1.41	1	0.020
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.334	U-shape	1.41	1	0.237
Distance between antennas	B	0.124	rectangular	1.73	1	0.072
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.051	normal	1	1	0.051
Near-field effects	B	0.111	normal	1	1	0.111
Total (k = 2)						0.59

f = 18000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.056	normal	1	1	0.056
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.052	U-shape	1.41	1	0.037
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.149	U-shape	1.41	1	0.106
Distance between antennas	B	0.124	rectangular	1.73	1	0.072
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power splitter asymmetry	B	0.030	normal	1	1	0.030
Adapter insertion loss	B	0.051	normal	1	1	0.051
Near-field effects	B	0.111	normal	1	1	0.111
Total (k = 2)						0.41

Travelling standard No 2. PA9852-20, s/n: 004

f = 18000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.003	normal	1	1	0.003
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.060	normal	1	1	0.060
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.036	U-shape	1.41	1	0.026
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.029	U-shape	1.41	1	0.020
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Directional coupler	B	0.071	normal	1	1	0.071
Adapter insert. loss (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Adapter insert. loss (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Total (k = 2)						0.29

f = 20000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.003	normal	1	1	0.003
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.061	normal	1	1	0.061
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.071	U-shape	1.41	1	0.050
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.031	U-shape	1.41	1	0.022
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Directional coupler	B	0.071	normal	1	1	0.071
Adapter insert. loss (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Adapter insert. loss (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Total (k = 2)						0.31

f = 22500 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.003	normal	1	1	0.003
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.060	normal	1	1	0.060
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.057	U-shape	1.41	1	0.040
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.034	U-shape	1.41	1	0.024
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Directional coupler	B	0.071	normal	1	1	0.071
Adapter insert. loss (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Adapter insert. loss (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Total (k = 2)						0.30

f = 25000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.003	normal	1	1	0.003
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.061	normal	1	1	0.061
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.071	U-shape	1.41	1	0.051
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.035	U-shape	1.41	1	0.025
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Directional coupler	B	0.071	normal	1	1	0.071
Adapter insert. loss (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Adapter insert. loss (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Total (k = 2)						0.31

f = 26500 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.005	normal	1	1	0.005
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.043	normal	1	1	0.043
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.062	normal	1	1	0.062
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.034	U-shape	1.41	1	0.024
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.044	U-shape	1.41	1	0.031
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Directional coupler	B	0.071	normal	1	1	0.071
Adapter insert. loss (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Adapter insert. loss (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Total (k = 2)						0.30

Travelling standard No 3. EMC2015-1, s/n: 005

f = 26500 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.004	normal	1	1	0.004
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.062	normal	1	1	0.062
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.014	U-shape	1.41	1	0.010
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.051	U-shape	1.41	1	0.036
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.100	normal	1	1	0.100
Directional coupler	B	0.071	normal	1	1	0.071
Adapter insert. loss (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Adapter insert. loss (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Total (k = 2)						0.35

f = 29000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.009	normal	1	1	0.009
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.060	normal	1	1	0.060
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.005	U-shape	1.41	1	0.004
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.030	U-shape	1.41	1	0.021
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.100	normal	1	1	0.100
Directional coupler	B	0.071	normal	1	1	0.071
Adapter insert. loss (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Adapter insert. loss (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Total (k = 2)						0.34

f = 32000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.008	normal	1	1	0.008
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.048	normal	1	1	0.048
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.059	normal	1	1	0.059
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.008	U-shape	1.41	1	0.006
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.060	U-shape	1.41	1	0.043
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.100	normal	1	1	0.100
Directional coupler	B	0.071	normal	1	1	0.071
Adapter insert. loss (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Adapter insert. loss (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Total (k = 2)						0.35

f = 36000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.007	normal	1	1	0.007
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.048	normal	1	1	0.048
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.062	normal	1	1	0.062
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.003	U-shape	1.41	1	0.002
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.087	U-shape	1.41	1	0.062
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.100	normal	1	1	0.100
Directional coupler	B	0.071	normal	1	1	0.071
Adapter insert. loss (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Adapter insert. loss (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Total (k = 2)						0.36

f = 40000 MHz

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
A-type uncertainty	A	0.010	normal	1	1	0.010
Power level meas. (trs. side)	B	0.053	normal	1	1	0.053
Power level meas. (rec. side)	B	0.067	normal	1	1	0.067
Mismatch error (trs. side)	B	0.005	U-shape	1.41	1	0.003
Mismatch error (rec. side)	B	0.151	U-shape	1.41	1	0.107
Distance between antennas	B	0.075	rectangular	1.73	1	0.043
Angle deviation	B	0.029	rectangular	1.73	1	0.017
Reflections inside chamber	B	0.100	normal	1	1	0.100
Directional coupler	B	0.071	normal	1	1	0.071
Adapter insert. loss (trs. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Adapter insert. loss (rec. side)	B	0.050	normal	1	1	0.050
Total (k = 2)						0.41

3.11 Annex A3

TECHNICAL PROTOCOL

**Supplementary Comparison of Antenna Measurements
between RISE (SWEDEN), TÜBİTAK UME (TÜRKİYE)
and CMI (CZECH REPUBLIC)**

Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II

22RPT04 RFMicrowave2

RISE

(Version 0.3)

April, 2024

Introduction

Horn antennas are commonly used in several different environments, for instance various electromagnetic research projects as well as in conduction testing for electromagnetic compatibility/interference (EMC/EMI). The calibration of the antennas can be done according to any of several different standards, for instance CISPR 16-1-6 (2014) [1], but must ultimately be traceable back to an NMI.

Within the project 22RPT04 RF Microwave 2, A EURAMET project started on May 01, 2023, a comparison between TÜBİTAK UME, CMI and RISE is to be conducted for horn antennas in the frequency range 1 GHz – 40 GHz.

The comparison will consist of the measurement of boresight antenna factor of three horn antennas at frequencies specified in Chapter 0. The boresight line is taken to be normal to the waveguide flange of the antenna and not normal to the aperture of the antenna. The antenna factor measurement will be carried out under the free-space condition.

RISE is acting as the pilot institute. The travelling standards will be provided by TÜBİTAK UME. RISE will be responsible to monitoring performance of travelling standards during the circulation and the evaluation and reporting of the comparison results.

The comparison will be carried out in accordance with the CCEM Guidelines for Planning, Organizing, Conducting and Reporting Key, Supplementary and Pilot Comparisons [2].

Travelling Standards

The travelling standards will be supplied by TÜBİTAK UME. The photos and the general specifications of the travelling standards are presented in Figure1 and Table 1, respectively.

Figure 1. Photos of the travelling standards; Double-ridged waveguide horn antenna 1–18 GHz (a), Horn antenna 18–26.5 GHz (b), Horn antenna 26.5–40 GHz (c)

Table 1. General specifications of the travelling standards

No.	Name	Manufacturer/Model	Serial number	General specifications
1	Double-ridged waveguide horn antenna	ETS-Lindgren Model 3115	00158093	Frequency range: 1 GHz – 18 GHz
2	Horn antenna	Pasternack / PA9852-20	004	Frequency range: 18 GHz – 26.5 GHz
3	Horn antenna	TÜBİTAK UME / EMC2015-1	005	Frequency range 26.5 GHz – 40 GHz

Participant Institutes

The pilot laboratory for this comparison is RISE. The participating institutes and contact persons with their addresses are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The information of the participant institutes

Country	Institute	Acronym	Shipping Address	Contact Person
Sweden	RISE Research Institutes of Sweden	RISE (Pilot laboratory)	Research Institutes of SWEDEN (RISE) Mats Cedheim/Hus 15 Brinellgatan 4, 504 62 Borås Sweden	Mats Cedheim mats.cedheim@ri.se Tel: +46 10 516 60 86
Türkiye	TÜBİTAK Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü	TÜBİTAK UME	TÜBİTAK Ulusal Metroloji Enstitüsü (UME) TÜBİTAK Gebze Yerleşkesi Barış Mah. Dr. Zeki Acar Cad. No:1 41470 Gebze-Kocaeli, Türkiye	Mehmet Çınar mehmet.cinar@tubitak.gov.tr Tel: +90 262 679 50 00
Czech Republic	CMI Český Metrologický Institut	CMI	Český metrologický institut Radiová 1136/3, 102 00 Praha, Czech Republic	Tomáš Pavlíček tpavlicek@cmi.cz Tel: +420 266 020 185

Time Schedule

The comparison will be organized in a single loop of three laboratories in order to allow close monitoring of the behavior of the standard. The time schedule for the comparison measurements is given in Table 3. If any deviation in the agreed time plan should occur, the pilot institute shall be informed.

Table 3. The time schedule for the comparison measurements

Participant	Country	Measurement Dates
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	8 April 2024 – 19 May 2024
RISE	Sweden	20 May 2024 – 14 June 2024
CMI	Czech Republic	21 June 2024 – August 2 2024
TÜBİTAK UME	Türkiye	12 August 2024 – 6 September 2024

Transport Case

All the travelling standards will be packed in one crate, which will be sent to RISE after the first measurements by TÜBİTAK UME. RISE will then start their measurements. The package contains the following antennas:

- Biconical antenna
- Log periodic antenna
- 3 horn antennas
- Monopole antennas

After RISE is finished with the measurements of each antenna, the transport is split up and the antennas will go to the next NMI so they can perform their measurements. After receiving the antennas, the participant must check for any damage of the items inside of the box. If the travelling standards have any damage due to transportation, this situation must be reported to the pilot laboratory.

When the participating NMI finish their measurements, the antenna shall be repackaged and sent back to RISE. RISE will then collect all antennas for transportation back to TÜBİTAK UME.

Transportation of Travelling Standard

The participants will be responsible for arranging transportation to the next participant.

The participants shall inform the pilot laboratory by e-mail when the travelling standards have arrived.

Failure of Travelling Standards

In case of any damage or malfunction of the travelling standards, the comparison will be carried out after either the travelling standards are repaired, or new standards have been designated.

Financial Aspects

Each participant institute is responsible for its own costs for the measurements as well as any damage that may occur within its country.

The overall costs for the organization of the comparison are covered by the pilot institute. The pilot institute has no insurance for any loss or damage of the travelling standard.

Measurement Points and Conditions

The comparison will consist of the measurement of boresight antenna factor of three horn antennas at frequencies specified in this chapter. The boresight line is taken to be normal to the waveguide flange of the antenna and not normal to the aperture of the antenna. The measured quantity is the antenna factor.

For horn antenna No. 1, the supplementary comparison frequencies are 1 GHz, 1.5 GHz, 2 GHz, 2.5 GHz, 3.5 GHz, 4 GHz, 5 GHz, 6 GHz, 7.5 GHz, 8 GHz, 10 GHz, 12 GHz, 14 GHz, 16 GHz and 18 GHz.

For horn antenna No. 2, the frequencies are 18 GHz, 20 GHz, 22.5 GHz, 25 GHz and 26.5 GHz.

And for horn antenna No. 3, the frequencies are 26.5 GHz, 29 GHz, 32 GHz, 36 GHz and 40 GHz.

The antenna factors must be measured for each frequency listed in Table 4.

Table 4. Measurement points & conditions

Relevant travelling Standard	Measurement frequency (GHz)	Condition
No 1. Model 3115	1	Distance 3 m AF_{3M}
	1.5	
	2	
	2.5	
	3.5	
	4	
	5	
	6	
	7.5	
	8	
	10	
	12	
	14	
	16	
18		
No 2. PA9852-20	18	Distance $\geq \frac{2D^2}{\lambda}$ Distance 3m (Far-field antenna factor AF)
	20	
	22.5	
	25	
	26.5	
No 3. EMC2015-1	26.5	
	29	

	32	
	36	
	40	

To monitor the condition of each travelling standard, participants will also provide the pilot laboratory with the reflection coefficient values valid in the reference plane of the antenna connector (antenna operating in free space condition) measured at the frequency points listed in Table 4.

Method of Computation of the Reference Value

The reference value and associated uncertainty for each test point will be a weighted mean and weighted uncertainty, respectively, calculated from the results of two participating laboratories. The antennas shall also be measured by TÜBİTAK UME prior to shipment to RISE and on its immediate return from RISE, and an additional component of uncertainty will be applied for the stability of the instrument transformer derived from the spread of those results.

The Comparison Reference Value (CRV) is calculated separately for each parameter. The CRV is considered as an estimation of the measurand according to the measurements provided by the participating laboratories. This estimation, x_{ref} , is determined as a weighted mean of the provided results where the weights are the inverse values of the squares of the associated standard uncertainties [3], [4], [5].

The weighted mean x_{ref} of the data set and the associated expanded uncertainty $U(x_{ref})$ are obtained from

$$x_{ref} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{U^2(x_i)}} \quad (1)$$

and

$$U^2(x_{ref}) = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{U^2(x_i)}} \quad (2)$$

Calculation of degrees of equivalence

The results of the comparison are reported as the degrees of equivalence (DoE) and the CRV.

The degrees of equivalence of each participant are calculated as:

$$D_i = x_i - x_{ref} \quad (3)$$

Where x_i is the results of the participant and x_{ref} is the CRV.

The expanded uncertainty of the degree of equivalence for a participant's result $U(D_i)$ is calculated as:

$$U^2(D_i) = U^2(x_i) - U^2(x_{ref}) \quad (4)$$

For each participant's result, the normalized error (E_n) is calculated as:

$$E_n = \frac{|D_i|}{U(D_i)} \quad (5)$$

The participant results are regarded as satisfactory if $E_n \leq 1$.

As only three participants are involved in the comparison, the outlier exclusion criterion will not be applied and all results from participating laboratories are included in the analysis.

Measurement Instructions

Precautions

Avoid extreme temperature, humidity or pressure changes as well as violent impacts.

Before the Measurements

The antennas should be allowed to stabilize in a temperature and humidity-controlled environment for at least 1 day before commencing measurements.

Before the measurements, mechanical controls of the antennas should be done, including pin depth of the connector.

Environmental Conditions

The ambient temperature and humidity must be measured. No corrections will be performed for temperature and humidity effects.

Preferably, the measurement equipment should be in a temperature-controlled room at 22 ± 2 °C. The passive antennas do not vary significant variation in its performance in the temperature range -5 °C to $+35$ °C.

Method of Measurement

The antenna factors will be measured at 3 m distance between apertures, in boresight at frequencies specified in Chapter 0. The boresight line is taken to be normal to the waveguide flange of the antenna and not normal to the aperture of the antenna. The supplementary comparison will be conducted by measuring the antennas in free space conditions, with each laboratory selecting its own method. The measurement method chosen by each participant will be thoroughly described in the measurement report. The measured quantity is the antenna factor.

Simplified measurement configuration of antenna pair is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Simplified measurement configuration of antenna pair

It is assumed that the measurement method will always be based on the measurement of the insertion loss between a pair of antennas. The obtained values are then used to calculate the antenna factor. The insertion loss will be always related to the reference planes of the coaxial connectors of the respective antenna pairs in a 50Ω measurement system.

When considering the radiation of the antennas in free space, for a distance of 3 m, the far-field condition is satisfied at all frequencies given the dimensions of antennas No. 2 and No. 3.

Due to the aperture size of the No. 1 antenna, the far-field condition is not met at some frequencies (approximately 6 GHz and above). For double ridged horn antennas, the so-called phase center shifts more significantly with frequency changes [6]. If the far-field condition is not met, the antenna factor AF_{3M} obtained for a prescribed distance of 3 m will be different from the antenna factor AF corresponding to the far-field condition. The measurements of each participant will therefore be subject to a systematic error (should be the same for all participants). Additional corrections to compensate for non-compliance with the far-field condition will therefore not be applied.

However, the part of the error that is due to the disregard of the phase center of the second antenna, which is paired with the AUT, must be adequately included in the measurement uncertainty.

Hence, for the purposes of this comparison, it is preferred that the other antenna, which forms a pair with the antenna under test (AUT), would operate in the far-field under free space condition at a distance of 3 m from its aperture with respect to its dimensions.

Measurement Uncertainty

The uncertainty of measurement shall be calculated according to the JCGM 100 “Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement” [2] for the coverage probability of approximately 95%.

The detailed measurement uncertainty budget is provided for each frequency listed in Table 4.

The example uncertainty budget shown below for the calculation antenna factor may be used by participant laboratories. In the event of other the sources of the uncertainty, the participant laboratories could apply them in the uncertainty table given below page.

Table 5. Example of uncertainty budget

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of Hz						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
Transmit antenna mismatch	B					
Receive antenna mismatch	B					
Effect of the site	B					
....	B					
....	B					
....	A					
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						

Reporting of Results

For the measurement results of the participants, the measurement report format given in Annex A will be used and the measurement report containing the measurement results of the participants will be sent to the pilot laboratory by e-mail within three weeks after the completion of the measurements.

Final Report of the Comparison

The pilot laboratory is responsible for the preparation of a comparison report.

The draft version of the comparison report will be issued within two months after receiving the participant report by the pilot institute. Draft report will be sent to the RISE for discussion and approval. This draft will be confidential to the participants.

The participant will have two weeks to send their comments on Draft Report. After approval, Draft Report will become the Final Report. The Final Report will form the basis for the publication of results.

References

- [1] CISPR 16-1-6, "Radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus - EMC Antenna calibration", Edition 1.1, 2017-1
- [2] CCEM Guidelines for Planning, Organizing, Conducting and Reporting Key, Supplementary and Pilot Comparisons, Ver. 2.1, 2017 (available on the BIPM website: https://www.bipm.org/utis/common/pdf/CC/CCEM/ccem_guidelines.pdf).
- [3] Evaluation of measurement data - Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM), JCGM 100, First edition, September 2008 (available on the BIPM website: http://www.bipm.org/utis/common/documents/jcgm/JCGM_100_2008_E.pdf)
- [4] Randa, J.: Proposal for KCRV & Degree of Equivalence for GTRF Key Comparisons, NIST, August 2000
- [5] Randa, J.: Update to Proposal for KCRV & Degree of Equivalence for GTRF Key Comparisons, NIST, February 2005
- [6] Harima, K.: Determination of gain of double-ridge guide horn antenna by considering phase center, NICT, Japan, IEICE Electronic Express, Vol. 7, Bo. 2, 86–91

3.12 Annex B3

Measurement Report for Development of RF and Microwave Metrology Capability II (22RPT04 RF&Microwave2)

Participant Information

Institute Name	
Contact Person	
Telephone No	
Fax No	
E-mail	
Address	

Measurement Date

Measurement Dates –
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References Used In Measurement

Name of Equipment	Manufacturer	Type / Model	Serial No

Measurement Procedure

Measurement Results

Table. Measurement results.

Relevant travelling Standard	Measurement frequency (GHz)	Antenna Factor (dB(1/m))	Measurement Uncertainty (dB), (k =2)	Ambient Temperature (°C)	Ambient Humidity (%rh)
No 1. Model 3115	1				
	1.5				
	2				
	2.5				
	3.5				
	4				
	5				
	6				
	7.5				
	8				
	10				
	12				
	14				
	16				
18					
No 2. PA9852-20	18				
	20				
	22.5				
	25				
No 3. EMC2015-1	26.5				
	29				
	32				

	36				
	40				

Detailed Uncertainty Budget

Uncertainty budget @ the frequency of GHz						
Source of uncertainty	Type	Value	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						